

Strengthening Democratic Governance
for Climate Transitions

D2.3: Interactions between climate change mitigation scenarios and climate democracy (D6)

WP2 – Analytical and empirical underpinnings

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Grant Agreement Number	101132661	Acronym	RETOOL	
Full Title	Strengthening Democratic Governance for Climate Transitions			
Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-05			
Funding Scheme	HORIZON EUROPE – Research and Innovation Action (RIA)			
Start Date	February 2024	Duration	36 Months	
Project URL	https://retoolproject.eu			
EU Project Advisor	Samuela Caramanica			
Project Coordinator	Dublin City University – DCU			
Deliverable	D2.3: Interactions between climate change mitigation scenarios and climate democracy (Deliverable number 6)			
Work Package	WP2 – Analytical and empirical underpinnings			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/07/2025	Actual	31/07/2025
Type of Deliverable	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	HOLISTIC S.A.			
Responsible Authors	Georgios Xexakis [HOL]			
	Dimitra Spatharidou [HOL]			
	Ioanna Bala [HOL]			
Contributors	-			
Reviewer(s)	Diarmuid Torney [DCU]			
Keywords	democracy; governance; climate policy; scenarios; integrated assessment.			

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of Action (DoA)

Based on the description in the DoA, this task would assess which “democratic structures and movements” are implicitly assumed in or are consistent with the narratives of climate change mitigation scenarios. The main difference with the task description is that we examine *overall characteristics* of democratic governance instead of specific democratic structures and movements in each country, as these aspects are not covered by the narratives or the quantifications of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways that underpin most available scenarios. Additionally, this task aimed to determine links between climate democracy and the impacts and assumptions from the IPCC AR6 Scenario Database, based on relevant literature and interviews with experts within and outside of the consortium. While the assessment of these links was indeed based on a literature review, it was supplemented by an extensive data analysis of the scenario results (see Section 5) instead of the expert interviews that are suggested in the DoA. The reason for this change was that the data analysis allowed us to explore patterns within most of the available scenarios, while the interviews would have realistically needed to focus on some indicative scenarios, potentially limiting the breadth of our assessment. Nevertheless, we have frequently elicited feedback from our RETOOL colleagues for this analysis in project meetings. We have also organised a meeting between political scientists and scenario modellers to discuss our assessment’s approach and explore further synergies based on this work. Otherwise, there were no other changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is mainly for use within the project consortium and within the wider communities of political science and climate-economy modelling, with the aim to support synergies between them.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

Climate action is deeply intertwined with socioeconomic development and governance structures. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) were developed to provide context for this interaction and help researchers understand how human choices can shape our climate. Towards this goal, this report analyses and compares the assumptions of different SSPs in terms of the future evolution of democratic structures and institutions in model-based studies. First, we use the Narrative Policy Framework to analyse how these scenarios reflect, embed, or omit democratic principles such as participation, representation, accountability, and justice. We find that narratives that explicitly centre democratic participation, institutional responsiveness, and justice, such as SSP1, are rare within climate scenario modelling, yet they are essential for envisioning legitimate and inclusive climate transitions. Second, we evaluate quantitative indicators within the SSP framework under the lens of the same core democratic characteristics. We find that examined indicators diverge significantly from the patterns of democratic governance implied in the SSP narratives. For instance, even in the widespread regional conflicts assumed in the SSP3 narrative, indicators for government effectiveness and human development do not decrease for almost any country by 2050. Third, by analysing scenarios from the 6th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, we find that regions that score high in indicators related to democratic characteristics tend to also perform well in climate change mitigation, aligning with relevant empirical research. These findings highlight opportunities to enhance the SSP framework so that it more accurately reflects democratic governance within scenarios and modelling exercises.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report and its respective GitHub repository¹, providing access to the scripts used for data analysis in this work and all resulting data visualisations.

¹ https://github.com/i2amparis/retool_scenario_analysis

Preface

The overall goal of the RETOOL project is to advance our understanding of how to address the twin challenges of responding to the climate imperative while strengthening and reinvigorating democratic governance. The project has four overarching objectives: (i) To deepen our understanding of the relationship between democratic governance and the climate imperative by developing a novel analytical framework and creating new empirical underpinnings, including important new open-access datasets; (ii) To understand how a variety of democratic institutions across Europe are responding to the climate challenge, including learning lessons from history and studying new and innovative democratic practices; (iii) To contribute to reinvigorating democratic governance in Europe by developing and synthesising new knowledge and insights on climate democracy, and presenting them in a range of high-impact formats; and (iv) To serve as a bridge between academic research on climate democracy innovations and policymakers and practitioners, as well as civil society and the wider public. RETOOL brings together an international and interdisciplinary consortium, with partners from Western Europe (Ireland, UK, Belgium, Austria), Northern Europe (Finland), Eastern Europe (Estonia), and Southern Europe (Italy, Greece), combining expertise in political science, political sociology, deliberative democracy, environmental law, European studies, and public administration. The consortium includes a democracy practitioner foundation (DDF), and all partners are closely associated with practitioner and civil society networks and involved in hands-on activities. RETOOL will be undertaken by a mature, settled consortium that has significant experience of working together, with six of our nine partners core members of the EU-funded Jean Monnet Network GreenDeal-NET.

Consortium Partner	Acronym	Country	Logo
Dublin City University	DCU	IR	
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB	BE	
Università degli studi di Trento	UNITN	IT	
Universiteit Gent	UGent	BE	
Universität für Bodenkultur Wien	BOKU	AT	
University of Eastern Finland	UEF	FI	
HOLISTIC S.A.	HOL	EL	
Foundation for Science and Liberal Arts Domus Dorpatensis	DDF	EE	
London School of Economics and Political Science	LSE	UK	

Executive Summary

Climate action is deeply intertwined with socioeconomic development and governance structures. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) were developed to provide context for this interaction and help researchers understand how human choices can shape our climate. Each pathway explores how key socioeconomic factors might evolve under specific assumptions about demographics, governance, technology, and economic development. These pathways serve as critical inputs for climate-economy models, enabling researchers to examine how different societal choices could lead to varying climatic outcomes and policy challenges, from SSP1's optimistic "green transition" world to SSP5's fossil fuel-dominated reality. This report analyses and compares the assumptions of the five SSPs in terms of the future evolution of democratic structures and institutions in model-based studies.

First, we use the Narrative Policy Framework to analyse how these scenarios reflect, embed, or omit democratic principles such as participation, representation, accountability, and justice, which constitute key dimensions of the RETOOL analytical framework (Deliverable D2.1). We find that narratives that explicitly centre democratic participation, institutional responsiveness, and justice, such as SSP1, are rare within climate scenario modelling, yet they are essential for envisioning legitimate and inclusive climate transitions. Most other SSPs reproduce either technocratic optimism or systemic inequality, often without robust deliberative mechanisms or protections for vulnerable populations. These findings highlight a critical gap in current modelling frameworks as the political futures embedded in these scenarios are often insufficiently aligned with democratic norms and governance principles.

Second, we evaluate quantitative indicators within the SSP framework under the lens of the core democratic characteristics of the RETOOL analytical framework. We find that examined indicators diverge significantly from the patterns of democratic governance implied in the SSP narratives. For instance, even in the widespread regional conflicts assumed in the SSP3 narrative, indicators for government effectiveness and human development do not decrease for almost any country by 2050. Similar patterns are found by zooming into Europe, where democratic values, as represented in the SSP quantifications, are assumed to improve in this century, in contrast to the reality of the democratic backsliding that we recently experience in many European countries.

Third, by analysing scenarios from the 6th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, we find that regions that score high in indicators related to democratic characteristics tend to also perform well in climate change mitigation. For instance, regions that have high government effectiveness, rule-of-law, and control of corruption in 2020, tend to achieve significant reductions of CO₂ emissions and energy intensity between 2020 and 2050. These findings may relate to the impact of institutional quality in addressing the climate crisis (including aspects of effectiveness and accountability) and are largely aligning with the available empirical evidence.

These findings highlight opportunities to enhance the SSP framework so that it more accurately reflects democratic governance within scenarios and modelling exercises. In collaboration with climate-economy modellers, political scientists could provide the theoretical and empirical background to enrich the existing five narratives with more assumptions about democratic structures or even suggest new narratives to explore alternative political futures. Apart from strengthening the SSP narratives, the two communities could also improve the alignment of the quantitative elements of the SSPs with their narratives in the context of governance and democracy. Future modelling studies can also explore the interactions between climate action and democratic governance in more detail, by assessing scenarios with different democratic structures, levels of participation, and expressions of justice in various countries. RETOOL can play an important role on this direction, by providing a wealth of research on different domains of democracy in Europe which could be potentially feed in future modelling work.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Defining democracy and its core characteristics.....	2
2.1	Defining democracy	2
2.2	Core characteristics of democracy	2
3	Why democracy matters for climate action.....	5
3.1	The role of democracy in climate action	5
3.2	Democracy and climate action backsliding	6
3.3	Climate policies and democracy	6
3.4	The Shared Socioeconomic Framework and common critiques	7
4	Characteristics of democracy in the SSP narratives.....	9
4.1	Introduction to qualitative approach	9
4.2	Methodology and analytical approach	10
4.3	Results	11
4.3.1	SSP1: Sustainability – Taking the Green Road	12
4.3.2	SSP2: Middle of the Road	13
4.3.3	SSP3: Regional Rivalry – A Rocky Road	14
4.3.4	SSP4: Inequality – A Road Divided	15
4.3.5	SSP5: Fossil-fuelled Development – Taking the Highway	16
4.3.6	Overview of the results	17
5	Characteristics of democracy in the quantification of the SSPs.....	18
5.1	Introduction	18
5.2	Methodology	19
5.3	Results	22
5.3.1	Proxies of participation in the SSPs	22
5.3.2	Proxies of representation in the SSPs	24
5.3.3	Proxies of accountability in the SSPs	25
5.3.4	Proxies of government effectiveness in the SSPs	27
5.3.5	Proxies of justice in the SSPs	28
6	Discussion and conclusions	30
6.1	Narratives	30
6.2	Quantification of narratives	31
6.3	Recommendations and next steps	32
7	References.....	34
8	Appendix	40
8.1	Use of SSPs in the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble	40
8.2	Percentage change of democratic characteristics proxies	41
8.3	Additional proxies of democratic characteristics in the SSPs	46
8.4	SSP proxies of democratic characteristics in Europe	49

Tables

Table 1. Implied assumptions of the SSP narratives in terms of core democratic characteristics	17
Table 2. Assumed links between the available quantitative components of SSPs and the core characteristics of democracy from the RETOOL analytical framework	20

Figures

Figure 1. The five Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) - reproduced by Oneil et al.	12
Figure 2. Count of IPCC AR6 scenarios per SSP	21
Figure 3. Projections of the Human Development Index per country based on the SSP extensions	23
Figure 4. Relationship between Human Development Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)	24
Figure 5. Projections of the Gender Inequality Index per country based on the SSP extensions	24
Figure 6. Relationship between the Gender Inequality Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)	25
Figure 7. Projections of the Rule-of-Law Index per country based on the SSP extensions	26
Figure 8. Relationship between the Rule-of-Law Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)	26
Figure 9. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions	27
Figure 10. Relationship between the Government Effectiveness Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)	28
Figure 11. Projections of the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient per country based on the SSP extensions	29
Figure 12. Relationship between the Rule-of-Law Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)	29
Figure 13. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions	39
Figure 14. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions	40
Figure 15. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions	41
Figure 16. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions	42
Figure 17. Projections of the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient per country based on the SSP extensions	43
Figure 18. Projections of Mean Years of Education per country based on the SSP extensions	44
Figure 19. Projections of Control of Corruption Index per country based on the SSP extensions	45
Figure 20. Projections of population share in extreme poverty per country based on the SSP extensions	46
Figure 21. Projections of the Human Development Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions	47
Figure 22. Projections of the mean years of education in Europe based on the SSP extensions	48
Figure 23. Projections of the Gender Inequality Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions	48
Figure 24. Projections of the Rule-of-Law Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions	49

Figure 25. Projections of Control of Corruption Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions	49
Figure 26. Projections of Government Effectiveness Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions	50
Figure 27. Projections of Gini Income Inequality Coefficient in Europe based on the SSP extensions	50
Figure 28. Projections of population share in extreme poverty in Europe based on the SSP extensions	51

1 Introduction

The IPCC's assessment of global mitigation progress reveals critical trends in how governance systems shape climate responses. Research indicates that democracies with strong participatory mechanisms tend to develop more robust climate policies. These systems show better compliance with international commitments, more effective decoupling of economic growth from emissions and greater CO₂ reductions. Electoral design plays a key role as representative systems outperform majoritarian ones and they allow better representation for climate-focused groups, reduce political risks for policymakers supporting ambitious measures and encourage stable, long-term climate commitments (Dubash et al., 2023). By 2020, democratic systems had implemented greenhouse gas legislation covering 53% of global emissions, demonstrating their capacity to translate climate concerns into enforceable legal frameworks (Calvin et al., 2023). This shows the growing role of democratic institutions in advancing climate governance through structured policies.

Climate change mitigation and adaptation present profound challenges that are deeply intertwined with socioeconomic development and governance structures. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) represent a novel framework in climate science, developed by researchers to better understand how human choices shape our climate future. Unlike older models that focused mainly on physical factors like greenhouse gas emissions, the SSPs combine both environmental and human elements by examining how policy decisions, technological progress and social changes interact with climate. The five scenarios depict different futures and each pathway explores how key socioeconomic factors might evolve under specific assumptions about demographics, governance, technology, and economic development. These scenarios serve as critical inputs for climate models, enabling researchers to examine how different societal choices could lead to varying climatic outcomes and policy challenges, from SSP1's optimistic "green transition" world to SSP5's fossil fuel-dominated reality, where climate action becomes extremely difficult. What makes the SSPs truly innovative is their foundation in hard data—they use detailed projections of population trends, economic growth, and urban development to create plausible future worlds. These pathways outline plausible global trajectories that would create distinct challenges for both climate change mitigation and adaptation throughout the 21st century (Andrijevic et al., 2019; de Bruin et al., 2022; Foster 2020; Peng et al., 2021; O'Neill et al., 2017).

To assess how future climate governance might evolve, this report analyses how different SSP scenarios shape the projected demand for democratic institutions and citizen-led movements. The report starts with a summary of key democratic characteristics that were defined by RETOOL in its analytical framework (Section 2) and a literature review of potential roles of democracy in climate action (Section 3). Subsequently, a narrative policy framework is employed to examine which democratic structures are implicitly assumed or supported within the textual narratives of the SSPs, revealing the normative visions embedded in these scenarios (Section 4). Similarly, a meta-analysis of scenarios used in the 6th Assessment Report (AR6) of the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) is used to identify implied relationships between democratic characteristics and indicators for climate change mitigation performance (Section 5). Finally, Section 6 integrates the results of the quantitative and qualitative analysis to provide recommendations for climate-economy modellers and political scientists, including the members of the RETOOL consortium.

2 Defining democracy and its core characteristics

In order to answer the core research questions that underpin the RETOOL project, we need a shared understanding of democracy. To do this, the project's analytical framework was used to define democracy and identify its seven core characteristics (Brawley-Chesworth et al., 2024).

2.1 Defining democracy

The most basic definition of democracy describes it as a system where leaders are selected through free and fair elections (Held 2006; Cini & Felicetti 2018). However, most contemporary understandings incorporate additional democratic ideals like citizen participation, deliberative processes, and representative governance (Lidskog & Elander 2007; Lafont 2015; Jacquet et al. 2023). These expanded definitions typically include fundamental freedoms such as press independence, association rights, judicial autonomy, and mechanisms holding officials accountable to affected populations (Pickering et al. 2022; Lindvall & Karlsson 2024).

While electoral processes form democracy's foundation - as none of the other democratic aspects can exist meaningfully outside an electoral framework - elections alone don't constitute a complete democracy. Electoral systems primarily follow two models: majoritarian (winner-take-all) systems where top vote-getters in districts win seats, and proportional systems that allocate legislative representation according to each party's vote share (Dahl & Shapiro 2020, p. 131), along with hybrid systems blending these approaches.

The concept of liberal democracy serves as another fundamental principle, emphasizing protections for minority groups against majority domination. This is achieved through institutional checks and balances coupled with individual rights safeguards (Locke, 1963; Holmes & Novick, 1995; Lindberg et al., 2014). Unlike systems concentrating authority in a single executive branch, liberal democracies distribute power across multiple government institutions (Held, 2006). While this design mitigates risks of oppression and instability, it may sacrifice some governance efficiency. Historically, the evolution of liberal democracy and broadening of rights have involved continuous social struggles and demands for greater inclusion (Tilly, 2017; Castañeda, 2023).

2.2 Core characteristics of democracy

Within the RETOOL project's core analytical framework, we identify seven cross-cutting characteristics of democracy: participation, representation, knowledge and expertise, accountability, deliberativeness, effectiveness, and justice. The categories were drawn from the existing literature about democracy across different fields of study and, therefore, reflect different perspectives on evaluating democracy. Some of the categories (for example participation) are largely procedural, some (such as effectiveness) are more related to outcomes, while others (for example, justice) include both. In addition, some characteristics have multiple elements (for example, accountability includes elements of responsiveness, achieving intended outcomes, and transparency). Importantly, several of the concepts below have conceptual overlap, with some scholars making distinctions where others do not. We have tried to indicate where there are significant differences of opinion in the literature.

Participation is the ability of citizens to engage in governance processes, both within and beyond elections is central (Graham et al 2003; Lidskog & Elander 2007). It can be direct (e.g., referenda) or indirect (e.g., electing representatives) (O'Flynn 2019; Koirala et al. 2021). While some argue excessive participation may destabilize governance (Hardin 2009), others highlight its normative, instrumental, and substantive benefits (Stirling 2006). In climate policy, participation is debated, some see it as slowing action, while others recognize it as essential for justice (Armeni & Lee 2021; Pickering et al. 2020). Armeni and Lee (2021) argue that, during a crisis, public participation can be seen by some as an unnecessary luxury that will slow down action, and that some view the public as too ignorant and selfish to adequately participate in climate change decisions, despite evidence that participation improves decision making. However, participation is included as a key element in the Aarhus Convention because of its importance in decision making and of its essential role in promoting justice (Pickering et al. 2020; Robinson and Shine 2018).

Representation looks at how much influence individual citizens have over outcomes, and is therefore a

measure of political influence, not just raw participation (Lidskog and Elander 2007). The concept of representation is used in several different ways. In the most common usage, it refers to one entity being authorised to speak for others, such as through elections (Brown 2006; Hayat 2022). Representation is also sometimes equated with responsiveness in the sense of looking at how institutions and governance systems try to serve all stakeholders (Graham et al. 2003). Another meaning relates to a person's embodiment of a specific social identity, such as race or gender (Brown 2006; Hayat 2022). These last two meanings are sometimes, but not always, included in definitions of participation, as the two concepts are closely related (Brown 2006).

Representative democracies have been criticised for having inherent disincentives to taking climate action due to periodic election cycles prioritising short-term wins over long-term problems (Lidskog and Elander 2007). In addition, as pointed out by Goodman and Morton (2023), representative democracy, as practised today, is widely seen as being highly influenced by the fossil fuel sector, which serves to prevent actions in the long-term interest of society. Similar to the discussion of participation and climate change, representing the interests of all who are (or will be) impacted by climate policies is a challenge to democratic systems.

There is also a robust dialogue in the literature about the representativeness of democratic experiments around climate change, such as mini-publics and other deliberative democratic innovations. Critics argue that mini-publics cannot represent the public because they are not authorised by those they seek to represent, and because once they have participated in the deliberation they no longer represent a cross-section of the public, but rather the views of what the public would think if they had been similarly educated (Lafont 2015). Others have argued that mini-publics are representative of the public in other ways.

Knowledge and expertise, and their use in informing policy, are important elements of democratic practice. Democratic decision-making should integrate diverse knowledge, including scientific, indigenous, and traditional systems (Lidskog & Elander 2007; Fiorino 2018). Climate governance relies on science, yet scientific knowledge is often politicized (Hulme 2009). Broader inclusion of social sciences and humanities is needed (Overland & Sovocool 2020; Rosamond et al. 2024). Indigenous knowledge poses challenges for democratic integration (Schlosberg & Collins 2014; Pickering et al. 2022).

Accountability describes the way a decision-making system attains its intended goals and remains answerable to those impacted by its decisions. While accountability is often equated with good governance, encompassing aspects like transparency, equity, democracy, efficiency, responsiveness, and integrity, thereby becoming a broad and somewhat ambiguous concept Bovens (2007, p. 450) offers a narrower, sociological definition. He describes it as "a relationship between an actor and a forum, where the actor must explain and justify their actions, the forum can question and evaluate them, and the actor may face repercussions." One approach to embedding accountability in governance is ensuring broad access to justice, including rights such as fair trials, effective remedies, equality before the law, and impartial, independent, and fair procedures (Palombella, 2021).

However, accountability becomes particularly challenging in climate governance, as existing democratic structures are not designed to hold decision-makers answerable to non-citizens (particularly those outside their jurisdiction), future generations, or non-human entities (Pickering et al., 2020; Koirala et al., 2021; Smith 2021). Deliberative democratic innovations address accountability differently—while they do not make final decisions, they must justify their recommendations, serving as advisory bodies to those ultimately accountable to the public (Brown, 2006; Bächtiger et al., 2018).

Deliberativeness of democracy refers to the degree to which laws and policies are agreed through "respectful and reasonable dialogue" (Lindberg et al. 2014, p. 160). The push for greater deliberation on climate change has been a key factor behind the rise of climate-related democratic innovations (Torney, 2021; Willis et al., 2021). This trend stems, at least in part, from criticisms that democratic decision-making fails to adequately prioritize scientific evidence and factual analysis (Jasanoff, 2013).

Effectiveness can be assessed in multiple ways. Broadly, it involves evaluating whether a democratic system achieves its intended outputs (e.g., laws and policies) and outcomes (e.g., the realization of policy goals and international commitments) (Lindvall & Karlsson, 2024). Democracies can also be judged based on procedural quality, including participation, representation, and accountability.

In the context of climate change, effectiveness further requires ambition proportional to the crisis—though this is complicated by uncertainties over global targets and equitable burden-sharing among nations. Other policy-focused indicators include long-term implementation capacity, adaptive policy design, and the inclusion of outputs, outcomes, and impacts (Jordan & Moore, 2022; Lindvall & Karlsson, 2024).

Justice is a multifaceted concept encompassing equality, self-determination, sovereignty, human rights, and access (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). While access to justice—often understood as the ability to engage with legal systems—is crucial, a broader perspective extends beyond it (Pickering, 2020; Palombella, 2021).

In climate change, justice has been framed as a human-centred approach that integrates human rights and development, prioritizing the most vulnerable while ensuring equitable sharing of climate impacts and solutions. Within such broad conceptions of justice, Zimm et al. (2024) identified five elements of justice for climate research—distributional, procedural, recognitional, corrective, and transitional.

Distributive justice focuses on equitable allocation of environmental burdens and benefits, addressing systemic inequalities in environmental degradation impacts (Schlosberg, 2013; Shue, 1992; Fiorino, 2018). Procedural justice ensures inclusive participation in decision-making for all groups (Zimm et al., 2024), while recognitional justice validates marginalized perspectives including Indigenous and non-Western knowledge systems (Cini & Felicetti, 2018; Pickering et al., 2022). Corrective justice seeks redress for historical wrongs (Zimm et al., 2024), and transitional justice prioritizes fair sequencing of climate actions. Together, these principles inform the concept of a just transition - a pathway to decarbonization that remedies past inequities while preventing future injustices (McCauley & Heffron, 2018), creating a framework for equitable and accountable climate governance.

These seven core characteristics of democracy all interact with each other. No two democracies are exactly alike, but all of them wrestle with questions of how to structure their institutions and bureaucracies around these varying characteristics, and changing how one is handled can influence others.

3 Why democracy matters for climate action

3.1 The role of democracy in climate action

The significance of democracy in the effectiveness of climate mitigation efforts is frequently underestimated. While some argue that the climate crisis might demand more authoritarian solutions, democratic governance remains the only political system capable of delivering sustainable and equitable climate adaptation (Nomikos, 2025). The RETOOL project is underpinned by the normative position that democracy is the only governance system capable of delivering both legitimate and effective solutions to this existential crisis, and that democracy plays a pivotal role in determining whether societies can achieve effective climate mitigation and adaptation (Gills & Morgan, 2019).

Democratic governance offers important advantages in addressing climate challenges. One key strength lies in its capacity for policy innovation and integration which enables the development of comprehensive approaches that combine technological and behavioural solutions. Democratic systems also have better adaptive governance capabilities, facilitating dynamic interactions between civil society, political actors, and local communities. Furthermore, they show greater potential to overcome implementation barriers that hinder climate action. While all governance models face systemic constraints, democratic processes are uniquely equipped to address challenges like political commitment gaps and civic engagement deficits through their accountability mechanisms and participatory decision-making structures (Calvin et al., 2023).

Democratic systems play a crucial yet complex role in climate policy, shaped by representation, participation, accountability, and justice. Political actors translate public demands into policies. However, their responsiveness varies with electoral cycles and partisan interests. Accountability mechanisms, such as litigation, help enforce climate commitments, while deliberative processes promote evidence-based policymaking. Also, justice considerations shape climate governance through equity, inclusion and recognition of marginalized perspectives that can influence policy design. Yet, effective democratic climate action depends on balancing participation and deliberation. Persistent challenges, highlight the need for institutional reforms that strengthen long-term climate commitments while maintaining democratic responsiveness and fairness (Dubash et al., 2023).

Democratic governance systems tend to produce more effective and equitable climate action through their characteristics of inclusive participation, institutional checks and balances, transparent decision-making, and accountability mechanisms. Democratic accountability mechanisms (e.g. courts, free press, and civic activism) are critical to countering short-termism in climate governance (Low et al., 2025; Selseng et al., 2021). These democratic qualities directly influence a society's adaptive capacity by ensuring that mitigation policies reflect local needs, distribute costs fairly, and maintain public legitimacy over time (Dryzek et al., 2019). Another advantage of democratic governance is that it necessitates that mitigation and adaptation policies address not only technical feasibility but also distributive justice, procedural fairness and recognition of diverse vulnerabilities (Schlosberg, 2013).

Additionally, electoral accountability in democracies pushes leaders to address public demands for climate action. However, democratic governments face a tension between short-term electoral incentives and the long-term benefits of climate policies (Clulow, 2018). Democratic systems, by design, encourage policymakers to respond to public demands and it is proven that democracies are more likely to adopt climate policies when voters prioritize environmental issues (Bernauer & Gampfer, 2013). Yet, electoral cycles also incentivize short-termism, where leaders avoid investing in long-term climate policies and prefer to focus on immediate economic interests.

Democratic institutions offer the essential frameworks for inclusive involvement in climate policy decision-making, guaranteeing that different communities are included in mitigation strategies (Dubash et al., 2023). Landmark cases like *Urgenda Foundation v. Netherlands* demonstrate how courts can enforce state accountability, while federal systems allow policy experimentation (Dubash et al., 2023). Finally, democratic systems facilitate civic mobilization and public advocacy, that are necessary to counter fossil fuel interests

(Gills & Morgan, 2019).

Unlike top-down policymaking, deliberative processes allow communities to voice their concerns and build consensus on mitigation measures. This not only improves the legitimacy of climate policies but also strengthens public willingness to support and comply with them (Leino & Kulha, 2023). Deliberative democratic processes, which prioritize meaningful public engagement, are seen as key to improving both the legitimacy and effectiveness of climate policies (Ross et al., 2021). Empirical evidence demonstrates that democracies consistently outperform authoritarian regimes in climate action. Clulow's (2018) research shows that democracy has a significant influence on greenhouse gas emission levels. The quality of democracy in domestic politics affects emission levels, with nations having more stringent regulatory frameworks generally producing lower emissions. For instance, nine of the top ten performers in the 2025 Climate Change Performance Index are democracies reflecting the structural advantages of democratic systems (Burck et al., 2024).

3.2 Democracy and climate action backsliding

Democratic institutions are facing the threat of backsliding due to the rise of populist and authoritarian regimes which can also undermine climate mitigation and adaptation. Nevertheless, democratic systems are more effective at driving climate innovation and policy stability compared to authoritarian regimes. Research shows that democracies produce more climate-related patents per capita, as decentralised problem-solving accelerates technological diffusion (Godfrey, 2025). While authoritarian regimes may enforce rapid decarbonization, such as China's renewable energy expansion, they often lack mechanisms to correct ineffective policies and they show suppression of dissent and elite-driven maladaptation (Low et al., 2025; Nomikos, 2025). Additionally, authoritarian regimes lack mechanisms for public accountability or equitable adaptation planning and amplify climate injustice. By centralizing power and dismantling checks and balances, these systems enable policy capture by vested interests (Paterson et al., 2023; Pickering et al., 2020).

Democratic backsliding, fuelled by populism, polarization, and corporate lobbying, further destabilizes climate action. Leaders like Brazil's Bolsonaro or France's Marine Le Pen have weaponized anti-climate sentiment, portraying policies as out of touch with public concerns and triggering green backlash. This backlash creates a vicious cycle: populist parties benefit from anti-climate rhetoric, continuing policy instability that delays meaningful action. For instance, the Bezos Earth Fund's withdrawal of support for the Science Based Targets initiative during the Trump administration proves how authoritarian-leaning leadership can derail even corporate climate accountability (Nomikos, 2025; Westton, 2025).

Studies show that democracies exhibit 19–27% higher climate adaptation readiness than autocracies. This is a result of the decentralised decision-making, free expression that can expose governance flaws and civil society pressure for accountability. Moreover in Europe, "70% of EU illiberal democracies missed 2023 climate targets due to weak enforcement, versus 30% in liberal democracies" (Oberthür et al., 2025, p. 9).

To confront these challenges, democracies must promote inclusive climate governance, ensure transparent policy design, and combat disinformation. By doing so, they can mitigate backlash, maintain stability, and deliver more equitable and effective climate solutions, which prove that democratic resilience remains essential in climate crises (Low et al., 2025; Nomikos, 2025; Selseng et al., 2021).

3.3 Climate policies and democracy

The IPCC's assessment of global mitigation progress reveals critical trends in how governance systems shape climate responses. Research indicates that democracies with strong participatory mechanisms tend to develop more robust climate policies. These systems show better compliance with international commitments, more effective decoupling of economic growth from emissions and greater CO₂ reductions. Electoral design plays a key role as representation systems outperform majoritarian ones and they allow better representation for climate-focused groups, reduce political risks for policymakers supporting ambitious measures and encourage stable, long-term climate commitments (Dubash et al., 2023). By 2020, democratic systems had implemented greenhouse gas legislation covering 53% of global emissions, demonstrating their capacity to translate climate concerns into enforceable legal frameworks (Calvin et al., 2023). This shows the growing role of democratic institutions in advancing climate governance through structured policies.

However, democratic systems are not without their weaknesses. The IPCC specifically identifies "economic lock-ins" and fossil fuel lobbying as major barriers, where the very diversity of representation in democratic frameworks can paradoxically allow established industries to delay or weaken climate measures (Calvin et al., 2023). This tension highlights the need for institutional reforms to counterbalance disproportionate influence while preserving democratic principles.

The effectiveness of climate policy depends more significantly on the quality of democracy, particularly in terms of participatory procedures and accountability systems, than on regime type alone. This has important implications for understanding how different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) might leverage or constrain democratic advantages in future climate governance (Calvin et al., 2023).

Formal institutions such as legislative bodies, party systems and bureaucratic frameworks create path-dependent constraints that resist rapid transformation, even when institutional changes might theoretically enhance mitigation outcomes (Dubash et al., 2023). While some authoritarian regimes adopt ambitious climate targets, their long-term success remains uncertain. Research suggests that democratic systems provide more reliable frameworks for sustained climate governance. However, these systems need safeguards against veto points and corruption to reach their full potential (Dubash et al., 2023).

3.4 The Shared Socioeconomic Framework and common critiques

The current SSP framework's treatment of governance is simplified and presents a critical limitation in the ability to project realistic climate adaptation scenarios. Climate scenarios often treat institutions as static, overlooking how democratic dynamics enable or constrain climate policy. Although the pathways recognise significant variations in governance across different scenarios, they do not adequately reflect the way in which democratic institutions influence the processes of adaptation. When analysing climate adaptation within the SSPs, integrating democratic indicators becomes essential for many reasons (Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022; Cherp et al., 2018).

While the SSP scenarios outline various governance trajectories, they insufficiently take into account how illiberal and authoritarian regimes exacerbate climate vulnerabilities. Populist leaders frequently dismiss climate research, framing environmental regulation as elitist impositions, while authoritarian systems centralise power, diminishing accountability and exacerbate climate injustice by minimizing equitable adaptation planning (Godfrey, 2025).

Modern climate change research requires robust frameworks to analyse the complex interplay between societal development and environmental outcomes. Developed through a collaborative international effort spanning climate science, economics, and energy systems modelling, the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) provide researchers with a comprehensive toolkit for integrated, cross-disciplinary assessment. These pathways outline plausible global trajectories that would create distinct challenges for both climate change mitigation and adaptation throughout the 21st century. (Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022; Cherp et al., 2018; Peng et al., 2021; de Bruin et al., 2022).

While the SSPs project aggregate socioeconomic trends, they fail to account for how democratic systems mediate climate action through political processes, where questions of who participates in decision-making and whose voices are heard become essential. Climate models are frequently criticised by researchers for their democratic deficit which is underlined in three critical dimensions. First is the exclusion of pluralistic values in scenario construction, the acceptance of expert authority in climate futures and the systematic depoliticization of mitigation choices. By framing climate response as primarily a technical optimization challenge, these models obscure the political nature of energy transitions and marginalize alternative ways that emerge from civil society. Recent efforts to incorporate political perspectives in IPCC assessments (AR6) suggest growing institutional awareness of these limitations. However, climate models try to predict future scenarios that scientists can agree on, but in reality, climate policy involves tough debates about policy priorities. This creates a mismatch between how models work and how real policy gets made (Clift & Kuzemko, 2024).

Additionally, the SSP framework's neglect of justice principles undermines its democratic legitimacy and policy relevance. They don't consider who gets included in decisions, or how different groups are affected. This makes them less useful for real-world policy, especially in places affected by climate changes and a democratic

system could prevent conflicts through its participatory mechanisms. The SSPs offer static perceptions of inequality, without integrating models of democratic instruments for redistribution, such as progressive taxation or green subsidies. Most importantly, the framework does not accommodate hybrid regimes that maintain electoral processes while undermining institutional checks on power, which is an emerging governance trend with significant implications for climate issues (Beck & Oomen, 2021). This critique highlights the need for more climate models that recognize how political decisions shape our climate future. By making the assumptions behind these models open for public discussion, we could better connect models with real-world policy.

Another critique on SSPs comes from Low et al. (2025) for treating "democracy" as a binary (cooperative vs. fragmented), ignoring other actors and judicial interventions that shape real-world outcomes. "Scenario models assume national governments are sole decision-makers, neglecting cities, courts, and grassroots movements that drive change" (p. 8). Democratic backsliding threatens to lock societies into high-emission, low-justice pathways. Future climate modelling must explicitly integrate these political dynamics, as the absence of democratic protection correlates strongly with mitigation failure and maladaptation. Strengthening climate action requires not just technological solutions but defending the pluralist institutions that make equitable, science-based policymaking possible (Paterson et al., 2023; Pickering et al., 2020).

Krawczyk & Braun (2025) use critical theory to emphasize that SSPs are not impartial tools but rather political constructions that reinforce established power dynamics and unsustainable standards. These models tend to prioritize specific worldviews while marginalizing other possibilities, thereby influencing strategies for adapting to climate change. Their research advocates for a critical examination of SSPs delving into whose interests they serve and how they influence policy, and it proposes incorporating diverse knowledge, challenging ideological assumptions, and placing justice and participation at the core of modelling to promote the democratization of climate action. Section 4 provides a more detailed analysis of the relationship between democratic governance and the SSPs based on the narrative policy framework.

4 Characteristics of democracy in the SSP narratives

4.1 Introduction to qualitative approach

This section adopts a qualitative approach to explore the complex interactions between climate change mitigation scenarios and climate democracy, with a particular focus on the narratives presented in the IPCC AR6 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Specifically, it uses the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) to analyse how these scenarios reflect, embed, or omit the core characteristics of democracy identified in the RETOOL framework.

The SSPs construct coherent storylines that describe how potential global societal trends, such as population growth, economic development, technology, and governance, might evolve over the 21st century. These narratives provide essential qualitative context to support quantitative models used in climate projections (Riahi et al, 2017). Although they are not intended for direct use by policymakers, they play a crucial role as analytical tools for climate change researchers preparing climate policy analysis in order to link different disciplines and sectors and function as a key data source (van Vuuren et al., 2017).

However, the core assumptions of the SSPs have been the subject of increasing scrutiny. Critics have noticed gaps in the frameworks, including a lack of attention to future human vulnerabilities (Rohat, 2018), shortcomings in the economic growth models (Buhaug & Vestby, 2019) and a disconnect between the economy and emissions trajectories (Bretschger, 2024). More recently, researchers have argued that the failure to systematically integrate justice and political development factors, such as institutional strength, rule of law, and political conflict, which significantly shape both mitigation capacity and vulnerability to climate risks, limits the scenarios' capacity to portray real world conditions that shape climate governance (Low et al, 2025; Leininger et al., 2024).

The modellers do acknowledge that certain projections are subject to large uncertainties, governance barriers being among them (Dellink, 2017). This recognition is especially important given the well-documented limitations of IAMs, which underpin many SSPs, as these models often simplify or omit critical socio-political dimensions such as power relations, agency, and justice that are central to democratic governance and require qualitative inquiry to be fully understood (Krawczyk & Braun, 2025). Social complexity is rarely portrayed in IAMs beyond purely economic behavior and, even there, the whole world is composed of a number of rational and farsighted agents who make rational decisions about the future (Mathias et al, 2020).

This need for a more politically attuned and context-sensitive approach has also been recognised by leading IPCC authors, who note that "policy research is facing a growing challenge: the literature is uncoordinated, investigating a wide variety of policies with few assumptions in common across studies," (O'Neill et al, 2020, p.1076). Attempts in the past to address this limitation have led to Shared Policy Assumptions (SPAs), which aim to better capture governance contexts and implementation barriers (Kriegler et al., 2014).

Qualitative research is essential for unpacking the discursive and ideological foundations of the SSPs. As Hulme (2022) notes, the scientific knowledge embedded in climate models is always shaped by its socio-political context as models are constructed in particular places, by particular institutions, and reflect particular political cultures. A qualitative, interpretive reading of these scenario narratives can help reveal the assumptions, omissions, and framing choices that guide our imagination of future worlds.

Building on this insight, this section applies the NPF to examine how democratic characteristics are constructed, or omitted, in the SSPs. This approach focuses on the core narrative elements identified by the NPF: setting, characters (heroes, victims, villains), plot, and moral of the story (Jones et al., 2014). These elements provide a structured method for analysing whether and how narratives affirm, challenge, or obscure democratic governance.

The central research question guiding this section is how core democratic traits, as defined in the RETOOL analytical framework, are represented through the narrative elements of the SSPs. We focus on the narrative texts of the five Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), particularly their qualitative storylines as presented

in Riahi et al. (2017) and O'Neill et al. (2016), due to their central role in climate policy modelling and their narrative structure which lends itself to NPF analysis.

To explore this, the analysis further investigates what implicit assumptions about democracy are embedded in the settings, characters, and morals of each SSP narrative, and how these may shape perceptions of legitimacy and governance. It also examines which democratic elements are systematically absent or marginalised, and considers the implications this holds for inclusive and just climate governance.

4.2 Methodology and analytical approach

This section employs the NPF to examine how the SSPs construct assumptions about democratic governance. The NPF is a theory-driven approach to analysing policy narratives, which views narratives not as mere communicative devices, but as strategic tools embedded in policymaking processes. At its core, the NPF suggests that narratives influence public opinion, policy coalitions, and institutional design by shaping how actors assign meaning to political events and decisions (Jones & McBeth, 2010; Shanahan et al., 2011).

Narratives are comprised of recognisable elements: a setting, characters (heroes, victims, and villains), a plot, and a moral of the story, often implying or justifying a specific policy solution (Jones & McBeth, 2010). These narrative structures are consistently found across political discourse and provide a common grammar through which policy actors convey meaning and mobilise support.

The analytical strength of the NPF lies in its ability to operate across multiple levels of analysis: a) Micro-level, which focuses on how individuals process narratives and form policy preferences (Jones, McBeth, & Shanahan, 2014), b) Meso-level: Concentrates on policy subsystems and advocacy coalitions, examining how groups strategically construct narratives to mobilise allies, define conflict, and influence policy outcomes and c) Macro-level: Though less developed, this level engages with the broader cultural and institutional contexts that shape and are shaped by dominant policy narratives (Shanahan et al., 2013). Democratic processes in governance are embedded in language, values, and institutional norms that are often subtle and contested (Farrelly, 2019), and the NPF provides a lens to make these dynamics visible and analytically tractable.

This section focuses primarily on the meso level, where narrative analysis intersects most directly with institutional and democratic concerns. At this level, the NPF is especially adept at revealing how narratives serve as tools of coalition-building and strategy and this is most relevant for understanding how narratives in the SSPs embed assumptions about governance and democratic legitimacy. The SSPs are not political blueprints, but their qualitative storylines play a critical role in shaping climate modelling and policy assessments. As previous research has shown, these storylines contain implicit visions of how societies might organise and govern themselves in the face of climate disruption (O'Neill et al., 2017; van Vuuren et al., 2017).

In the context of climate change, where the scale and complexity of the challenge often defy linear solutions, narratives become particularly powerful. They help actors navigate uncertainty, assign blame and responsibility, and envision possible futures. Scholars have increasingly emphasised the political and discursive dimensions of climate models and scenarios. For example, Hermwille et al. (2023) argue that climate narratives are not neutral, but moral and political interventions. Similarly, Calliari (2016) and Kanerva and Krizsán (2021) show how linguistic framing in climate negotiations and IPCC summaries can marginalise alternative values or prioritise economic growth over justice. This aligns with more recent multimodal discourse research, such as Wang and Huang (2023), which reveals how language use and discursive practices mediate climate communication across diverse platforms and stakeholders. The NPF offers a framework to render these dynamics visible and analytically tractable. Together, these studies underscore the centrality of discourse and narrative in shaping the politics of climate governance and legitimation, further affirming the relevance of applying the NPF to the SSPs.

To evaluate how the SSP narratives reflect or obscure democratic principles, this analysis integrates the NPF with the RETOOL framework's seven democratic characteristics: participation, representation, knowledge/expertise, accountability, deliberativeness, effectiveness, and justice. This dual lens enables us to

assess not only how each SSP structures its narrative elements, but also how it projects different visions of democratic governance and legitimacy.

The primary data source is the set of qualitative SSP narratives as presented in Riahi et al. (2017), O’Neill et al. (2017), and the IPCC AR6 Synthesis Report. These narratives were selected due to their prominence in climate research and their structured, storyline-based format, which aligns with the NPF’s analytical requirements. The SSPs offer five distinct world-building scenarios that serve as backbones for integrated assessment models (IAMs) used in global climate policy modelling.

Narrative elements were extracted through manual coding, using the NPF’s four key components:

- Setting: the socio-political and institutional context.
- Characters: identified actors such as governments, elites, citizens, or future generations.
- Plot: the causal mechanisms connecting decisions to outcomes.
- Moral: the implied or explicit policy direction or governance model.

Each SSP was assessed against these components, and then mapped against the seven RETOOL democracy characteristics. This structured coding allowed us to identify which democratic traits were present, marginalised, or absent across the five scenarios. For example, SSP1 includes explicit references to inclusive participation and institutional transparency, aligning with democratic ideals. By contrast, SSP3 describes authoritarian governance and restricted access to institutions, signalling democratic erosion.

A comparative matrix was created to synthesise these findings across SSPs. This matrix enabled a systematic evaluation of how democratic assumptions vary across scenarios and revealed patterns of inclusion, exclusion, and normative framing. Importantly, this approach goes beyond content description to illuminate the ideological foundations of each narrative, and the kind of political futures they make imaginable (Farrelly, 2019; Krawczyk & Braun, 2025). As Otto et al. (2021) argue, understanding and closely examining narratives in IPCC reports can open space for discussing desirable post-Paris futures.

4.3 Results

In this section, we present the results of the analysis for each of the five SSP narratives separately. For each pathway, we examine how the RETOOL core democratic characteristics are embedded or omitted across the narrative structure using NPF. These elements can be used to analyse the following:

- Setting: What are the assumed political, social, and economic contexts in each SSP scenario, including governance structures, legal parameters, and demographics? How do these elements frame the operating environment for democratic institutions and movements?
- Characters: How are different actors (governments, corporations, civil society, citizens, future generations) portrayed in the SSP narratives? Are they heroes solving problems, villains causing them, or victims suffering the consequences?
- Plot: What are the causal mechanisms described in the SSP narratives that connect actors and the setting to climate outcomes? Does the plot suggest that certain democratic actions or institutional structures are necessary or hinder progress?
- Moral of the Story: What policy solutions or outcomes are explicitly or implicitly advocated for in each SSP narrative? How do these align with actions taken by or demands placed upon democratic institutions and citizen movements?

The analytical questions used in this section were adapted from the NPF, as outlined in Jones et al. (2014), drawing specifically on the structural elements presented on page 6 (setting, characters, plot, moral of the story) and adapted to fit the thematic concerns of the RETOOL project. At the end of the section, a comparative matrix summarises the key differences and commonalities across the SSPs, offering a consolidated view of how various future scenarios align with or challenge democratic governance. It is noted that direct quotations

from the SSP scenario texts (O'Neill et al, 2017) are included in italics throughout the analysis in this subsection.

Figure 1. The five Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), reproduced from O'Neill et al. (2017)

4.3.1 SSP1: Sustainability – Taking the Green Road

SSP1 constructs a vision of a future where societies transition *gradually but pervasively* toward a more sustainable and equitable path, rooted in social inclusion, institutional cooperation, and human well-being. The narrative casts a broad coalition of actors such as governments, international institutions, civil society, and the private sector as central protagonists working together to reshape global development. These actors are presented as “*increasingly effective and persistent*” in their “*cooperation and collaboration*”, which facilitates *improved management of shared environmental resources* (text in italics from O'Neill et al, 2017, here and everywhere in this subsection). Citizens, while not directly named, are implied to be active participants in this transformation through “*changing perceptions*” and consumption patterns that align with sustainability and equity goals. The absence of explicit antagonists or villains supports a worldview in which no single group obstructs progress, but where challenges are systemic and require coordinated responses.

The setting imagined in SSP1 is one of increasing institutional strength, social cohesion, and political commitment to well-being and sustainability. It assumes a world where “*strong and flexible global, regional, and national institutions*” work in synergy to enable both mitigation and adaptation. Demographic dynamics are influenced by “*educational and health investments*” that “*accelerate the demographic transition*,” particularly in “*current high-income countries*,” leading to lower population growth and a renewed focus on human development. The institutional context shifts decisively away from extractive economic models, as “*the emphasis on economic growth shifts toward a broader emphasis on human well-being, even at the expense of somewhat slower economic growth over the longer term.*” Furthermore, “*inequality is reduced both across and within countries*,” indicating not only a redistributive governance model, but also one that enhances representation and social solidarity.

The narrative’s plot follows a causally coherent and hopeful trajectory. It begins with the recognition of the “*social, cultural, and economic costs of environmental degradation and inequality*,” which serves as the catalyst for structural change. In response, policy shifts occur, most notably through “*investment in environmental technology and changes in tax structures*”, that lead to “*improved resource efficiency*,” lower emissions, and more sustainable consumption. Societal behaviours also evolve, as “*consumption is oriented toward low*

material growth and lower resource and energy intensity,” suggesting a public willingly participating in the transition. These outcomes are not framed as the result of top-down enforcement but rather as the consequence of democratic deliberation, shared values, and institutional responsiveness. The scenario assumes that effective and participatory institutions guide these transformations, making it clear that democratic governance is integral to achieving sustainability. It also implies that adaptability, learning, and feedback mechanisms are embedded in governance processes, supporting long-term accountability.

The moral of the SSP1 narrative is that a better, fairer, and more sustainable world is achievable through deliberate, inclusive, and well-coordinated action across all levels of society. Institutions are expected to serve the public interest, not just in terms of economic performance, but in facilitating *“improvements in human well-being.”* The story champions *“new global institutions”* that evolve to *“support cooperation on sustainable development,”* highlighting the importance of institutional reform and innovation. Technological advancement is aligned with democratic values, as renewable energy becomes more viable not through authoritarian mandates, but because of *“increased investment, financial incentives and changing perceptions.”* Importantly, the scenario does not frame environmental success in terms of control or dominance, but through responsiveness, fairness, and collaboration. The moral logic suggests that sustainability is not a trade-off with democracy but the result of it.

4.3.2 SSP2: Middle of the Road

The narrative of SSP2 portrays a world in which existing trends continue without major disruptions or breakthroughs. Unlike the more visionary or polarised trajectories of other SSPs, SSP2 presents a scenario defined by inaction and persistent structural limitations. The key characters in this narrative are national governments, global institutions, and societies more broadly which are positioned as moderately responsive but ultimately constrained. Institutions *“work toward but make slow progress in achieving sustainable development goals”*, suggesting that while political actors aim to improve governance, their efforts are limited by inefficiencies, lack of coordination, and limited political will as some countries *“fall short of expectations”*. The private sector and civil society are not highlighted as central agents, indicating a technocratic and state-centric governance model. Citizens appear indirectly, primarily as recipients of slow improvements in *“living conditions and access to education, safe water, and health care,”* but there’s no mention of their participation in the transition. This marginalisation implies that citizens have limited influence on shaping policy, reflecting a restricted form of representation and participation in the democratic process.

The setting of SSP2 is one of political stability coupled with developmental stagnation. The world is described as following *“a path in which social, economic, and technological trends do not shift markedly from historical patterns.”* This backdrop implies a maintenance of existing institutions and governance practices, with little ambition for systemic reform. While *“most economies are politically stable,”* the quality of that stability is ambiguous. *“Globally connected markets function imperfectly,”* and institutions *“make slow progress,”* pointing to weak global coordination and limited institutional responsiveness. Socially, the scenario is characterised by *“continuing societal stratification and limited social cohesion,”* with *“income inequality that persists or improves only slowly.”* These features indicate structural constraints on distributive and recognitional justice, where democratic institutions fail to fully address systemic challenges. Moreover, the narrative suggests that investments in global development are insufficient as *“education investments are not high enough to accelerate the transition to low fertility rates in low-income countries,”* revealing gaps in both knowledge inclusion and global equity. As such, the setting reflects a form of procedural democracy with limited substantive outcomes, where formal institutions exist but fail to generate transformative change.

The plot of SSP2 follows a gradual, almost stagnant progression. The causal logic links *“moderate development trends”* to *“moderate challenges to mitigation and adaptation,”* implying there’s limited institutional ambition and uneven social investment. Although *“technological development proceeds apace,”* the lack of *“fundamental breakthroughs”* underscores the absence of bold public intervention or innovation. Even environmental governance proceeds unevenly *“environmental systems experience degradation, although there are some improvements,”* a dynamic that reflects slow institutional learning and partial implementation of policy. Importantly, the scenario normalises fossil fuel use, noting that *“there is no reluctance to use unconventional fossil resources,”* which implies the persistence of politically difficult trade-offs. Overall, the plot suggests that democratic institutions remain formally intact but are underperforming in their deliberative, participatory, and

accountable capacities.

The moral of SSP2 is that a business-as-usual democratic model yields partial and uneven progress, insufficient for addressing the scale of climate challenges or deepening democratic legitimacy. While there is no collapse of institutions, there is also no systemic step forward. The narrative promotes a cautious realism in which existing systems endure but underdeliver. Social and environmental vulnerabilities remain high due to *“persistent inequality,” “limited social cohesion,”* and *“constrained advances in sustainable development.”* Implicitly, the scenario critiques the effectiveness of contemporary democratic institutions that fail to redistribute resources equitably or facilitate participatory transformation. By highlighting the heterogeneity of outcomes *“across and within countries,”* the narrative acknowledges deep structural inequities, yet offers no clear processes for resolving them.

4.3.3 SSP3: Regional Rivalry – A Rocky Road

The SSP3 scenario constructs a fragmented world order in which nationalism, regional competition, and authoritarian tendencies dominate the political landscape. The central characters in this narrative are countries and their governments which are portrayed as increasingly self-interested actors who prioritise national and regional security over global cooperation or collective well-being. This is made explicit in the opening sentence as *“a resurgent nationalism, concerns about competitiveness and security, and regional conflicts push countries to increasingly focus on domestic or, at most, regional issues.”* Global governance actors, including international institutions and civil society, are notably absent or severely weakened. The scenario references a *“limited number of comparatively weak global institutions, with uneven coordination and cooperation,”* suggesting that mechanisms for collective accountability and participation have largely eroded. The emergence of *“more authoritarian forms of government with highly regulated economies”* in several regions further constrains the scope for democratic participation, dissent, and civil liberties. Citizens, particularly marginalised and disadvantaged communities, are framed primarily as victims of systemic neglect, suffering from persistent inequality, *“struggling to maintain living standards”* and having reduced access to basic services like *“safe water, improved sanitation, and health care.”* Unlike SSP1, where cooperation and participatory processes are celebrated, SSP3 casts most actors in isolated roles, embedded in national silos and deprived of effective representation.

The political and institutional setting of SSP3 is one of de-democratisation, institutional fragmentation, and high social vulnerability. Governance is framed in terms of national security priorities, as *“policies shift over time to become increasingly oriented toward national and regional security issues.”* Trade barriers rise, particularly in energy and agriculture, undermining interdependence and collaborative problem-solving. The narrative makes clear that democratic governance is in retreat: *“in several regions (countries) move toward more authoritarian forms of government,”* reducing transparency, representation, and citizen participation. Institutions capable of addressing transnational challenges are *“ineffective,”* and in many regions altogether absent. The erosion of global coordination leaves disadvantaged countries especially vulnerable, as they *“struggle to maintain living standards and provide access to safe water, improved sanitation, and health care.”* These conditions reflect a governance landscape characterised by low justice, low deliberation, and minimal accountability, where state priorities are driven by control, not inclusion. Education and knowledge generation are devalued, with *“investments in education and technological development”* declining, further marginalising democratic discourse.

The plot of SSP3 unfolds through a logic of deterioration and fragmentation. As geopolitical tensions rise, states become more conservative and defensive. Rather than responding to global crises with cooperation, they raise barriers. This leads to a downward spiral of inequality, institutional weakness, and environmental degradation. The narrative details how *“economic development is slow,” “inequalities persist or worsen over time,”* and *“strong environmental degradation”* affects entire regions due to the *“low international priority for addressing environmental concerns.”* These patterns of decline are not simply incidental but are the product of deliberate policy choices that favor short-term national security over long-term climate stability or human development. The causal mechanisms here are *“resource intensity,” “fossil fuel dependency,”* and *“slow technological change”* as well the breakdown of institutions. The narrative ultimately links this cascade of political and economic failures to *“high challenges to mitigation”* and *“high challenges to adaptation for many groups in all regions.”* Implicitly, the plot conveys the consequences of absent democratic safeguards as when

participation, representation, and justice erode, so too does a society's capacity to respond effectively to climate risks.

The moral of the story in SSP3 is a cautionary one. It warns that a fragmented and authoritarian global system will fail not only to deliver sustainable development but will also amplify inequality, environmental harm, and human insecurity. Sustainability, in this scenario, becomes nearly unattainable due to the *"combination of impeded development and limited environmental concern."* The scenario does not present a path forward, but rather a breakdown of democratic legitimacy and capacity, where neither local nor global institutions are capable of protecting vulnerable populations or coordinating systemic change. The few remaining governance mechanisms are reactive rather than anticipatory. The erosion of global solidarity, alongside the dismantling of inclusive governance structures, leaves societies increasingly exposed. SSP3 presents a stark illustration of what happens when deliberative democracy, inclusive participation, and transnational accountability are not only neglected, but actively dismantled.

4.3.4 SSP4: Inequality – A Road Divided

This pathway describes a stark division in representation and influence, where it exists strongly for an elite but is severely lacking for vulnerable groups. The main characters in this scenario are divided along sharp socioeconomic lines. On one side is *"an internationally-connected society that is well educated and contributes to knowledge-and capital-intensive sectors of the global economy,"* while on the other is *"a fragmented collection of lower-income, poorly educated societies that work in a labor intensive, low-tech economy."* This duality is reinforced by a narrative structure that concentrates agency and influence in the hands of a *"relatively small political and business elite, even in democratic societies."* The elite are implicitly positioned as heroes within their own system as they are well-connected, mobile, and technologically adept, while vulnerable groups, explicitly mentioned as having *"little representation in national and global institutions,"* are cast as persistent victims of structural exclusion. Unlike SSP1's collaborative protagonists or SSP3's authoritarian villains, SSP4 defines characters primarily by their systemic roles in reproducing or suffering from inequality. There is no clear antagonist but rather, the villain is inequality itself, and the narrative's focus is on the strengthening of hierarchical systems that limit democratic responsiveness and participation.

The setting in SSP4 is defined by the erosion of democratic equity and the concentration of both political and economic capital. It describes a world where *"highly unequal investments in human capital"* and *"increasing disparities in economic opportunity and political power"* lead to growing *"stratification both across and within countries."* This signals a severe decline in procedural and substantive justice, where the conditions for equal representation and participation are actively undermined. While some societies retain the formal structures of democracy, the concentration of influence *"in a relatively small political and business elite"* results in a hollowing out of democratic institutions, particularly in relation to responsiveness to marginalised populations. The setting is marked by weak social cohesion, as *"conflict and unrest become increasingly common,"* and access to basic services such as *"water, sanitation and health care"* remains out of reach for many in low-income countries. This fragmentation leaves large portions of the population structurally excluded from meaningful political engagement, and with *"limited access to effective institutions for coping with economic or environmental stresses,"* their capacity to advocate for their needs or influence decisions is further diminished. While some sectors of the economy thrive, largely due to concentrated technology development, this progress is confined to the elite-controlled high-tech economy and fails to translate into broad societal resilience or inclusion.

The plot of SSP4 is driven by systemic division and institutional inaction. The growing inequality is not portrayed as an unintended side effect, but as a consequence of highly uneven development paths and political choices that favor elite consolidation. As *"power becomes more concentrated"* and *"vulnerable groups have little representation,"* governance mechanisms increasingly serve the interests of an elite class, sidelining deliberation and weakening the moral contract of inclusive democracy. While *"technology development is high in the high-tech economy and sectors,"* the benefits are constrained in the hands of the few. The plot further reveals how environmental governance becomes partial and uneven: *"environmental policies focus on local issues around middle and high income areas,"* leaving low-income and vulnerable populations without protection or adaptation strategies. Despite these disparities, the scenario claims *"low challenges to mitigation,"* not because of systemic cooperation, but due to the technical capacity and rapid-response

capability of “a *well-integrated international political and business class*.” However, this mitigation success comes at the cost of justice, equity, and democratic legitimacy. Meanwhile, adaptation is depicted as a deep structural challenge, since “*substantial proportions of populations*” face “*limited access to effective institutions*,” highlighting the failure of public systems to equitably support those most affected by climate and economic stresses.

The moral of the story in SSP4 is that progress for the few does not translate into justice for the many. While global elites are able to mobilise resources to mitigate emissions through capital and innovation, large portions of the world’s population remain trapped in vulnerability due to a lack of access, voice, and institutional support. The fact that such disparities persist “*even in democratic societies*” suggests a collapse of the normative foundations of democracy, where procedural form is maintained but substantive equality, representation, and accountability are eroded. The world described in SSP4 is not authoritarian in the classic sense, but rather plutocratic and exclusionary, where governance reflects the interests of a globally connected elite and neglects those at the margins.

4.3.5 SSP5: Fossil-fuelled Development – Taking the Highway

This narrative describes a world with strong formal participation and institutional effectiveness, but perhaps with a specific focus on market-oriented solutions. The central characters of this narrative are industrialised and emerging economies, competitive markets, and participatory societies which are presented as agents of progress. The narrative opens with a strong causal link: “*Driven by the economic success of industrialised and emerging economies, this world places increasing faith in competitive markets, innovation and participatory societies*.” Governments are largely supportive of market-based systems, and institutional actors focus on enabling rather than regulating participation. Importantly, disadvantaged groups are acknowledged in the storyline, though their agency appears to be facilitated rather than autonomous: “*interventions focus on maintaining competition and removing institutional barriers to the participation of disadvantaged population groups*.” These groups are not depicted as central protagonists in shaping the narrative but are offered a place within the system as beneficiaries of market inclusion. Overall, the characters are not adversarial and there are no clear villains but rather structured around the duality of elite-led innovation and broad human development, with an underlying assumption that progress will benefit all.

The setting of SSP5 is marked by institutional strength, economic optimism, and an overwhelming commitment to rapid growth and modernisation. This is a world in which “*global markets are increasingly integrated*,” where international mobility expands, and where governments invest heavily in public services. “*There are also strong investments in health, education, and institutions to enhance human and social capital*,” suggesting a deliberate effort to reinforce democratic infrastructure and human development. Participation is encouraged, at least in procedural terms, through “*participatory societies*,” while policy is geared toward liberalisation, “*gradually opening up labor markets*” and ensuring institutional access. However, this promising picture is complicated by the narrative’s environmental stance. The global community places “*relatively little effort to avoid potential global environmental impacts due to a perceived tradeoff with progress on economic development*.” Environmental sustainability is subordinated to growth imperatives, with the implicit assumption that technological solutions or even “*geo-engineering if necessary*” will be sufficient to manage long-term risks. The tension here is between democratic inclusion and ecological recklessness as, while participation is structurally enabled, intergenerational justice and environmental accountability are marginalised. The scenario reflects a setting in which democracy functions effectively at the national level but fails to integrate planetary boundaries or long-term responsibility into its framework.

The plot of SSP5 unfolds through a narrative of accelerating growth enabled by market mechanisms, innovation, and technocratic governance. The storyline connects “*faith in competitive markets*” and “*rapid technological progress*” to sweeping human development gains. Economic expansion is paired with formal social inclusion, creating a feedback loop in which “*income disparities decrease*” and “*international mobility is increased*.” This leads to “*rapid growth of the global economy*,” high levels of education and infrastructure investment, and enhanced global interconnectedness. However, the scenario does not question the underlying structure of fossil-fuelled development. On the contrary, it embraces it: “*the push for economic and social development is coupled with the exploitation of abundant fossil fuel resources and the adoption of resource and energy intensive lifestyles*.” Fossil fuels are not treated as a threat but as a vehicle for progress, while

environmental degradation is framed as a secondary issue that can be managed technologically or postponed. The result is a world with “*potentially high challenges to mitigation,*” not because of institutional weakness, but because of the intentional deferral of ecological responsibility. Democratic mechanisms of deliberation and accountability are present but directed primarily at economic performance rather than long-term sustainability.

The moral of the story in SSP5 is one of confidence in technocratic governance, market solutions, and engineered resilience. Human development goals are achieved, but through a form of democracy that prioritises output efficiency and global competitiveness over justice or ecological foresight. “*The attainment of human development goals, robust economic growth, and highly engineered infrastructure results in relatively low challenges to adaptation,*” the narrative tells us, suggesting that even in the face of climate disruptions, societies will be able to cope, provided they have the means. Yet this confidence is grounded in an unequal calculus: the scenario acknowledges that these benefits apply “*for all but a few,*” implying that vulnerable groups and low-income regions remain exposed to disproportionate risk. Climate responsibility, particularly in terms of emissions mitigation, is not deeply embedded in the social contract; it is treated as an externality, potentially manageable by future technologies. This shifts the moral orientation of the narrative away from justice and accountability and toward efficiency and innovation.

4.3.6 Overview of the results

Table 1 below presents a comparative matrix summarising how each of the five SSP narratives aligns with the seven core democratic characteristics defined in the RETOOL framework. Values range from “High”, indicating strong and explicit presence of a democratic feature, to “Very Low”, which signals its absence or active erosion within the scenario; “Medium” and “Low” represent intermediate levels of inclusion, uneven implementation, or weak normative support.

Table 1. Implied assumptions of the SSP narratives in terms of core democratic characteristics

SSP Scenario	Participation	Representation	Knowledge & Expertise	Accountability	Deliberativeness	Effectiveness	Justice
SSP1: Sustainability	High	High	High	High	High	High	High
SSP2: Middle of the Road	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low to Medium	Low to Medium	Medium	Medium
SSP3: Regional Rivalry	Low	Low	Low	Very Low	Very Low	Low	Very Low
SSP4: Inequality	Low	Very Low	Medium	Low	Very Low	Medium	Very Low
SSP5: Fossil-fuelled Development	High	Medium	High	Medium	Low	Low to medium	Low to Medium

5 Characteristics of democracy in the quantification of the SSPs

5.1 Introduction

Complementing the analysis of the SSP narratives in Section 4, this section aims to evaluate the quantitative elements of the SSPs under the lens of the core democratic characteristics identified in the RETOOL analytical framework. The quantitative elements play a crucial role in the practical application of the SSP conceptual framework as they are used as inputs in integrated assessment modelling (O'Neill et al., 2017). The initial quantitative elements of the SSPs included projections for basic modelling drivers within this century such as population data, GDP and education levels (Crespo Cuaresma, 2017; KC et al., 2024) and are available in the SSP Scenario Explorer². Throughout the years after the release of the SSP framework, more quantitative elements became available, providing future projections of aspects such as governance quality (Andrijevic et al., 2020), rule of law (Soergel et al., 2021), gender inequality (Andrijevic et al., 2025), extreme poverty (Crespo Cuaresma et al., 2018), and human development (Cuaresma & Lutz, 2024). Data for all these additional quantitative elements are provided in a unified format by the SSP Extensions Explorer³. While some of these indicators relate to democracy, such as government effectiveness or the rule of law, it is not always clear how well they align with the assumptions implied in the narratives. Also, other democratic aspects such as participation or representation are not explicitly mentioned in the SSP extensions.

In response to these gaps, the first objective of this section is to identify which of the available SSP quantitative elements could act as proxy variables for the core characteristics of democracy from the RETOOL framework. Subsequently, we will examine the projections of these proxy variables to uncover potential patterns between SSPs and compare them with the democratic assumptions from the SSP narratives. For instance, we examine the evolution of government effectiveness by the middle of the century for different countries, and we juxtapose these patterns with the narrative assumptions for the Effectiveness of democratic institutions that we identified in Table 1 at the end of Section 4. We can find proxy variables for five out of the seven characteristics of the RETOOL analytical framework: participation, representation, accountability, effectiveness, and justice. Relevant proxies are more difficult to find for the characteristic of deliberativeness and of knowledge and expertise (see next section for more details). Through this analysis we can then understand different variants of democracy that are assumed in the SSPs and, therefore, by the scenarios that use them, such as the scenario ensemble examined by the 6th assessment report (AR6) of the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC).

The second objective of this section is to examine the relationship between the implicit democratic assumptions in the SSPs and the evolution of pertinent indicators for climate change mitigation, as projected in the IPCC AR6 scenarios. The main motivation behind this objective was to uncover the implicit assumptions of IPCC AR6 scenarios in terms of democratic governance and understand the range of mitigation impacts that have been explored under different assumptions. For instance, does high governmental effectiveness enable countries to perform well in climate action? While the answer to such questions has been provided in the literature (Eisenack et al., 2014), it is helpful to understand whether such relationships align with the findings for the scenario results. The purpose of such analysis is not to use the IPCC AR6 results to prove these relationships between democratic elements and climate action. Instead, it is an opportunity to understand gaps in the scenario space of AR6 and identify entry points for future work that can enhance the representation of democratic elements in mitigation and adaptation scenarios. This representation can then be informed by the theoretical and empirical findings of RETOOL and contribute to the understanding of the links between climate and democracy in both communities of climate-economy modelling and political science.

² <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp/#/about>

³ <https://ssp-extensions.apps.ece.iiasa.ac.at/learn>

5.2 Methodology

In this section, we examine the full range of available SSP variables from the SSP Scenario Explorer and the SSP Extensions Explorer for potential links with the seven democratic characteristics that were identified in RETOOL. Based on these links, we then chose some SSP variables as proxies for the democratic characteristics which are then analysed in Section 5.3. All available SSP variables, along with their suggested links to democratic elements, can be found in Table 2 (see next page). These links are based on relevant political science literature, for instance, empirical studies that identify correlations between the democratic characteristics and the socioeconomic variables in the SSPs. In addition, the links have been informed by the first version of the Climate Democracy Index that has been elaborated as part of Task 2.3 of RETOOL. It is noted that these links are neither exhaustive nor aimed to cover the full range of dimensions that exist in each democratic characteristic. They instead aim to provide an indication of the direction of democracy in each SSP, based on the quantification of a relevant proxy. Overall, the following links have been

- **Effectiveness:** A government effectiveness indicator is already available in the SSP Extensions.
- **Accountability:** Projections for indicators on the quality of the Rule of Law index and the Control of Corruption are readily available in the SSP extensions and can be easily associated with the democratic principle of accountability (Rose-Ackerman, 1999; Schedler et al., 1999).
- **Participation:** Education has been frequently considered as an enabler of political participation (Jensen, 2025). Similarly, the Human Development Index, a composite indicator has been developed by UN and synthesises indicators related to education, health, and income, can be also enhanced through democratic participation (Harding & Wantchekon, 2010) and shows a positive correlation with democratic indices (UNDP, 2024).
- **Representation:** In the case of representation, the selection of proxies is much more challenging. For instance, we can assume that global regions that have low gender inequality, will have better gender representation in the political system and thus improve the quality of the representation overall (Mendelberg et al., 2014). Of course, representation in democratic institutions is not only affected by gender representation, but this is one of the most fitting indicators provided in the SSP framework and its extensions.
- **Justice:** While many SSP indicators relate to different dimensions of justice, we chose the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient and the share of population in extreme poverty as proxies to distributional justice.
- **Knowledge and expertise:** Despite the fact that SSPs and most IPCC AR6 scenarios are rather technocratic and based on innovation learning curves, there is no explicit variable referring to the knowledge and expertise of the government. A potential link can be made with governmental effectiveness or even with the overall educational level of the population, but it is rather indirect and uncertain.
- **Deliberativeness:** Similarly, there is no variable related to deliberativeness in the SSPs nor a potential proxy variable to aspects of this principle.

Table 2. Assumed links between the available quantitative components of SSPs and the core characteristics of democracy from the RETOOL analytical framework

SSP variables	Core characteristics of democracy						
	Participation	Representation	Knowledge & Expertise	Accountability	Deliberativeness	Effectiveness	Justice
SSP main variables v2024							
GDP PPP							
Population							
Population Urban Share							
Population Sex Age							
Mean Years of Education Sex Age	+	+	+				
SSP extensions							
Human Development Index	+	+	+				+
Governance Index	+	+	+			+	
Government Effectiveness		+	+			+	
Control of Corruption		+		+		+	
Rule-of-Law Index		+		+			
Gender Inequality Index	-	-					-
Gini Income Inequality Coefficient	-	-					-
Income Distribution (in deciles)		+/-					+/-
Employment Agriculture [Share]							
Employment Industry [Share]							
Employment Services [Share]							
Value Added Agriculture [Share]							
Value Added Industry [Share]							
Value Added Services [Share]							
Net Migration							
Net Remittances [per capita]							
Population Extreme Poverty	-	-				-	-
Population Risk of Hunger						-	-
Probability of Armed Conflict							
GDP PPP [Conflict-Adjusted Projections]							

Legend: + = assumed positive correlation, - = assumed negative correlation, +/- = selected proxy variable for the analysis.

To analyse the selected proxies, we first download all related datasets from the SSP Scenario Explorer and the SSP Extensions Explorer and read them using the pyam⁴ Python package. We then plot these variables in maps as shown in Section 5.3 using the pandas⁵ and geopandas⁶ libraries. To focus on the future evolution of these proxy indicators, we assess their change between 2020 and 2050 across all SSP variants. This period captures the early and critical phase of the transition. The year 2050 is particularly significant, as many countries have set it as a target for achieving net-zero emissions.

For the second part of the analysis, we jointly analyse the scenario data from the IPCC AR6 with the SSP indicators. A major challenge with this approach is the lack of variety of SSPs used in the AR6 scenarios, as the vast majority of the scenarios selected the SSP2 as a pathway (Figure 2). A potential reason for this imbalance is that assumptions in such studies are usually entering as alternative scenarios rather than as alternative runs of different SSPs. Another important point is that the set of AR6 scenarios is an ensemble of opportunity without structured ways of varying scenario ensembles (Peters et al., 2023; Sognaes & Peters, 2025). This imbalance is even more pronounced across different policy categories explored in the scenarios (see Appendix 8.1). Thus, it is not easy to compare insights directly between scenarios as most scenarios will have the same SSPs and thus assumptions related to democracy. Another challenge is the granularity of the results: AR6 scenarios provide results that are mostly global or are referring to large global regions such as Europe, Latin America, or Southeast Asia. Thus, most scenarios do not provide detail on impacts to individual countries, apart from major ones such as the USA or China.

Figure 2. Count of IPCC AR6 scenarios per SSP

To address these challenges, we will focus on the most granular level of results that is provided for most scenarios in the AR6 Scenario Explorer and Database⁷. This would be the R10 results, where the world is divided in 10 regions. The R10 regions are 1) Africa, 2) Eastern Asia (primarily China), 3) Europe (including Turkey), 4) South Asia (primarily India), 5) Latin America and the Caribbean, 6) Middle East, 7) United States and Canada, 8) the Pacific OECD countries (Australia, Japan, New Zealand), 9) former Soviet Union countries not included in Europe, 10) and the rest of Asian countries that are not included in the previous categories (e.g., Indonesia, Thailand, Viet Nam etc.). The exact country grouping per region is on the R10 description on GitHub⁸. We then select four pertinent indicators for assessing the effectiveness of climate change mitigation.

⁴ <https://pyam-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>

⁵ <https://pandas.pydata.org>

⁶ <https://geopandas.org>

⁷ <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ar6>

⁸ <https://github.com/IAMconsortium/common-definitions/blob/main/definitions/region/common.yaml>

The main indicator is the change of CO₂ emissions as this is one of the main results provided by most models and a typical parameter used by the modellers as a target for the modelled transition. Since the majority of the emissions come from the energy system, most models submitted energy-related results to the IPCC AR6 report. The other three selected indicators are related to the energy system but examine it from different perspectives. First, we look at the share of renewable energy sources (RES) as this is a very frequent indicator used for policy analysis. We then look at the energy intensity of the GDP as an indicator of energy efficiency and the carbon intensity of energy as another measure of success in decarbonising the energy system. The last two indicators are also part of the widely used Kaya identity which describes the most important drivers of CO₂ emissions.

As the last step in this process, we create a combined dataset where we join the dataset with the four mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 results and the proxies of democratic characteristics collected from the SSP extensions. We then plot results for all R10 regions and calculate a linear regression to show the relationship between each proxy variable and each transition indicator. For instance, do regions with high rule of law perform well in terms of reducing CO₂ emissions among the examined scenarios? As mentioned above, this relationship is mostly indicative to help us identify common assumptions used in the scenarios. It is important to emphasise that the IPCC AR6 scenario results are not a representative statistical sample as they are mostly collected as an ensemble of opportunity. Thus, the linear regression aims to help identify some underlying patterns rather than prove a correlation between variables. Nevertheless, we also use robust regression to address some of the assumptions of the linear regression and avoid issues with the sample, especially for SSPs 3 and 4 where available scenarios are limited.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Proxies of participation in the SSPs

As shown in Figure 3 based on data from Soergel et al. (2021), Human Development Index (HDI) in 2020 is shown to be highest for most OECD countries in Europe, Northern America, and Australia and New Zealand and lowest for many African nations. Interestingly, in all five SSPs, this indicator shows improvements from 2020 to 2050 for all countries, with the highest improvements shown for African countries and India in SSP1 and SSP5, bringing them more in line with countries that already had high HDI. Assuming that democratic institutions and structures are an enabler of this increased HDI in most countries (Harding & Wantchekon, 2010; UNDP, 2024), this may indicate that democratic participation is also increasing in all SSPs and throughout all countries. This is somewhat at odds with the expected trajectories of political participation from the narrative analysis (Section 4). For instance, SSP2 is expected to be a continuation of current trends but instead it seems that improvements in HDI (and, assumingly, in participation) are almost at the level of the high-development pathways SSPs 1 and 5. Additionally, the conflicts implied in the narrative of SSP3 and the rising inequalities in SSP4 do not significantly decrease HDI in any country, with HDI levels in those SSPs remaining rather stable by 2050—and even increasing for some countries. The same patterns can be found by looking only at education (Figure 14 in the Appendix). For instance, the mean years of education for the female population between 25 and 29 years old seem to increase in all SSPs in the same way as with the HDI.

Turning to impacts, Figure 4 shows that, in most of the examined scenarios that follow SSP1, SSP2, and SSP5, global regions that show significant reductions in CO₂ emissions between 2020 and 2025 show a high HDI in 2020. This finding is less robust in SSPs 3 and 4 where 95% confidence intervals are too wide to indicate any meaningful correlation. Similar patterns can be seen on the scenario outputs for the energy intensity of GDP which also seems to be positively correlated with HDI, even for scenarios that follow SSP3 and 4. In contrast, no clear patterns can be found for SSPs between HDI and the share of RES and between HDI and the carbon intensity. Taking again the assumption of a positive correlation between HDI and political participation, these findings indicate that high political participation may be positively correlated with CO₂ emissions reductions and improvements on energy efficiency in the examined scenarios.

Figure 3. Projections of the Human Development Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 4. Relationship between Human Development Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)

5.3.2 Proxies of representation in the SSPs

Based on the data from Andrijevic et al. (2025) that is visualised in Figure 5, Gender Inequality Index (GII) in 2020 was lowest for Western European countries, Australia, and Canada (0.1 to 0.2) and highest among several African countries (0.7-0.8). GII is significantly improved in almost all countries in 2050 for SSPs 1 and 5 (reaching values of 0.1-0.2), agreeing with the narratives of these SSPs that inequalities are reduced between and within countries. Assuming that in countries with low gender inequality all genders are adequately represented in democratic institutions, we can assume that democratic representation is rather improving in these SSPs. However, SSPs 3 and 4 also show improvements in gender inequality between 2020 and 2050 (and, presumably, in representation). While gender inequality in these SSPs still varies significantly among countries as it did in 2020, these improvements come at odds with the narrative analysis where inequalities seem to deteriorate (Section 4). Counterintuitively, SSP4 shows more improvements than SSP3, despite inequality being the definitive feature of the SSP4 narrative. SSP2 is a bit more in line with its narrative, as it shows moderate improvements while keeping the same patterns of inequality between countries. Thus, it is assumed that representation also improves between 2020 and 2050 in all SSPs, with SSPs 1, 2, and 5 being closer to their narratives.

Figure 5. Projections of the Gender Inequality Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Based on the scenario results of IPCC AR6, regions with low gender inequality in 2020 seem to perform better in terms of reducing of their CO₂ emissions and energy intensity of their GDP by 2050 (Figure 6). Similar to HDI in the previous section, this is shown most prominently for scenarios that follow SSP2, SSP1, and SSP5.

Patterns between GII and CO₂ emissions reductions are more unclear for SSP3 and SSP4 although some correlation is still indicated for these SSPs between GII and energy intensity. A rather positive correlation is also shown between GII and carbon intensity of energy for SSP2 although it is less strong than the one indicated for the aforementioned mitigation indicators. The connection between GII and RES share is even less clear for all SSPs. Assuming again a positive relationship between gender equality and representation in democratic institutions, these findings suggest that countries with high representation today can potentially achieve significant reductions of their CO₂ emissions and energy intensity.

Figure 6. Relationship between the Gender Inequality Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)

5.3.3 Proxies of accountability in the SSPs

Drawing from the data of Andrijevic et al. (2020), Figure 7 shows that the Rule-of-Law Index for 2020 was highest in Canada, Australia, and several Western European and Scandinavian countries and lowest for China, Libya, Venezuela, Somalia, and other countries in Africa. Rule-of-law seems to ameliorate in 2050 for most countries in the context of SSP1, except for Canada and the other countries that had already high Rule-of-Law Index where it is slightly reducing. However, SSP2 shows that rule-of-law is slightly reduced for most countries with the exceptions of China and Libya where it slightly improves. This deterioration is also found in SSP3, where the rule-of-law is reduced to similar levels as in SSP2, with some countries such as Chad or Sudan showing even further decline. Overall, it seems that the evolution of the rule-of-law—and, likely, accountability as a whole—among the three SSPs does not correspond to their respective narratives. Whereas the results here indicate little difference in accountability between the SSPs, the SSP1 narrative assumes high accountability in most countries, the SSP2 assumes low to medium accountability and the SSP3 assumes very low accountability. Differences between the SSPs are more pronounced for the control of corruption indicator (see Section 8.3), where SSP1 and SSP5 show improvements between 2020 and 2050 in all countries, with SSP3 and SSP4 showing similar levels of corruption in 2020 as in 2050, and SSP2 being somewhere between these two groups. This may indicate higher agreement between the narratives and their quantifications for this aspect of accountability.

Figure 7. Projections of the Rule-of-Law Index per country based on the SSP extensions

As shown in Figure 8, regions with high Rule-of-Law Index in the AR6 scenario ensemble show high reductions in CO₂ emissions, energy intensity, and carbon intensity for SSP1- and SSP2-aligned scenarios. There is an even more noticeable positive correlation between the Rule-of-Law index and the RES share for these SSPs, compared to the more ambiguous findings for HDI and GII. Findings for SSP3-aligned scenarios are more uncertain, with the exception of the relationship between rule-of-law and reductions in energy intensity that show a positive relationship, as in the case of the other SSPs. Similar positive correlations are found between control of corruption and reductions in CO₂ emissions and energy intensity, with less clear results shown for RES share and carbon intensity (Section 8.3). Overall, these results suggest that accountability may have a positive relationship with the examined mitigation indicators, especially CO₂ emissions and energy intensity.

Figure 8. Relationship between the Rule-of-Law Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)

5.3.4 Proxies of government effectiveness in the SSPs

Government effectiveness in 2020 follows similar patterns as with the HDI indicator (Section 5.3.1), with the highest effectiveness scores (0.8-1.0) found in Europe, North America, Australia, and New Zealand and the lowest effectiveness scores (0.1-0.2) found in African countries such as Libya, Chad, Sudan, and Somalia [Figure 9, based on data from Andrijevic et al. (2020)]. In SSP1 and SSP5, effectiveness is significantly improved in all countries between 2020 and 2050, reaching an effectiveness score higher than 0.6 in almost all countries and with many OECD countries reaching the maximum score. The improvement in effectiveness is less pronounced in SSP2, although still more than half of the countries reach an effectiveness score of 0.6 in 2050. Interestingly, effectiveness patterns for SSP4 are similar to the ones of SSP2 in 2050, while the patterns in SSP3 are noticeable worse and approaching the state of the indicator in 2020. While these patterns follow the ones implied by the narrative analysis in Section 4, i.e., SSP1 and SSP5 have the highest effectiveness, SSP2 and SSP4 are moderate and SSP3 is the lowest, the quantified effectiveness projections are not varying significantly between SSPs. Additionally, there is no deterioration of effectiveness, even in the case of the extensive conflicts between countries that are implied in SSP3.

Figure 9. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Governmental Effectiveness also shows a positive correlation with the assumed reductions in CO₂ emissions and energy intensity in the AR6 scenarios that follow SSP1, SSP2, and SSP5 (Figure 10), following similar trends as with all previous indicators. This is an intuitive finding as countries that feature high governmental effectiveness in this decade may be in a better position to implement the policies required for the transition.

This relationship is much more uncertain for all other SSP, between effectiveness and RES share, and between effectiveness and carbon intensity of energy.

Figure 10. Relationship between the Government Effectiveness Index and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)

5.3.5 Proxies of justice in the SSPs

As a proxy for the justice dimension of democracy, the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient for 2020 was lowest (around 30-35%) for most of Western Europe, Scandinavia, and Canada and highest (around 60-70%) for South Africa, Brazil, Mexico, and Colombia [Figure 11, based on data from Rao et al. (2019)]. The Gini coefficient significantly improves in 2050 projections for SSP1 and, especially SSP5, where almost all countries reduce income inequality apart from Canada and the USA where inequality slightly rises. Among the most significant improvements is China, where the Gini coefficient falls from 45% in 2030 to 30% in 2050 for SSP5 and 34% for SSP1. These patterns of improvements from 2020 to 2050 are also evident in SSP2 but to a slightly less extent. SSP3 and SSP4 show a deterioration of the Gini coefficient, suggesting that incomes become much more unequal within most of the countries. The only exceptions to this are Mexico and Bolivia in SSP4, where inequality decreases. In contrast to the other proxies examined before, these patterns of the Gini coefficient better match the expectation from the narrative analysis, i.e., that inequalities are reduced in SSP1 and SSP5, that are more or less continuing in SSP2, and that are exacerbated in SSP3 and, especially, SSP4. This pattern does not hold though for the other indicator of justice, the share of population in extreme poverty (Section 8.3), where poverty is reduced in most countries without much variation among SSPs.

Figure 12 shows another way that the Gini coefficient does not follow the same patterns as other proxies examined here: the relationship between the Gini coefficient and all four mitigation indicators in the AR6 scenarios is rather unclear for most SSPs. There is only a positive correlation found for SSP2 scenarios between the Gini coefficient and the reduction of CO₂ emissions and the increase of RES share, but this is rather weak in contrast to the correlations found for most other indicators. Stronger indications for a correlation are shown for the other potential proxy for justice (Section 8.3 in the appendix), where regions with low share of extreme poverty in SSP2 have low energy and carbon intensity as well as high RES share. Still, these signals are not found for the other SSPs, suggesting that the interaction between justice dimensions and climate change mitigation is much more complex than the way it is examined here.

Figure 11. Projections of the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 12. Relationship between the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient and mitigation indicators from the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble (per R10 region and SSP)

6 Discussion and conclusions

6.1 Narratives

Across all five SSP narratives, we identify a number of recurring patterns in how democratic structures, values, and institutional assumptions are constructed. These patterns which were revealed by applying the Narrative Policy Framework and the RETOOL analytical framework offer insights into the democratic imaginaries embedded in global climate governance scenarios. While the SSPs are not policy blueprints, they function as normative storylines that shape how climate futures are modelled, debated, and politically imagined (Poznic & Hillerbrand, 2021). In this section, we summarise the key findings of our qualitative narrative analysis and reflect on their broader significance for democratic governance in climate transitions.

Our first main finding is that SSP1 stands out as the only scenario that consistently embeds strong democratic assumptions across all RETOOL dimensions. It portrays a world in which cooperation, equity, and institutional responsiveness are central. Civil society, governments, and international institutions are framed as collaborative protagonists, and governance is depicted as inclusive, participatory, and adaptive. The plot of SSP1 emphasises that systemic transformation toward sustainability is possible through strong democratic capacities, particularly deliberation, representation, and accountability. The narrative suggests that democratic governance is not a hindrance to climate action, but rather its enabling condition.

In contrast, SSP2 presents a vision of procedural democracy without transformation. While democratic institutions formally exist, they are portrayed as slow, uneven, and only partially responsive to societal needs. Participation is constrained, social cohesion is limited, and institutions make “slow progress” on sustainability goals. The narrative represents a warning that without democratic innovation and commitment to justice, political stability alone may not deliver meaningful climate action or legitimacy.

Our third main finding is that SSP3 and SSP4 exemplify scenarios of democratic decline, though in different forms. SSP3 narrates a collapse of democratic coordination, with the rise of authoritarian regimes, nationalist fragmentation, and weakened institutions. Participation and representation are actively suppressed, and citizens are framed as victims of state-led exclusion. In SSP4, democratic institutions remain formally intact in some regions but are hollowed out by economic stratification. The scenario presents a world where “power becomes more concentrated in a relatively small political and business elite,” (O’Neill et al., 2017) and where vulnerable groups are excluded from decision-making. In both narratives, democratic characteristics such as justice, deliberation, and accountability are either absent or structurally undermined.

Finally, SSP5 depicts a hybrid model of democracy that is highly technocratic and market-driven. The scenario upholds formal participation and invests heavily in education and human capital, but it subordinates ecological and intergenerational justice to economic growth. The plot emphasises institutional effectiveness and innovation, but the narrative moral is shaped by a logic of efficiency and global competitiveness rather than equity. Democratic structures are instrumentalised to support fossil-fuelled development rather than reoriented toward sustainable governance.

From our cross-scenario analysis, we conclude that narratives that explicitly centre democratic participation, institutional responsiveness, and justice, such as SSP1, are rare within climate scenario modelling, yet they are essential for envisioning legitimate and inclusive climate transitions. Most other SSPs reproduce either technocratic optimism or systemic inequality, often without robust deliberative mechanisms or protections for vulnerable populations. These findings highlight a critical gap in current modelling frameworks as the political futures embedded in these scenarios are often insufficiently aligned with democratic norms and governance principles.

These findings align with and reinforce recent calls to integrate questions of equity and inclusion more directly into scenario design. As Andrijevic et al. (2025) argue, representing gender inequality in scenario narratives significantly alters our understanding of societal capacity to adapt to or mitigate climate change. Their work demonstrates that current SSPs often underrepresent the political, institutional, and distributive consequences

of gendered access to resources, decision-making, and public goods. Similarly, Leininger et al. (2024) highlight that political development, such as institutional quality, regime type, and accountability, is currently acknowledged but not meaningfully integrated in the SSPs, leading to an underestimation of the barriers to effective climate action. Both papers underscore the need to expand the challenge space to include political variables that capture not only climate feasibility, but also democratic legitimacy and institutional resilience. Our analysis complements these critiques by showing that many SSP narratives reproduce assumptions of elite-driven or technocratic governance while underemphasizing participatory and justice-based pathways.

6.2 Quantification of narratives

The main finding from the first part of the quantitative analysis was that the SSP variables that are used as proxies to democratic characteristics diverge significantly from the patterns implied by the SSP narratives. Most proxy variables are improving in all countries from 2020 and 2050, even in SSPs where democracy is expected to decline such as in SSP3 and SSP4. As mentioned in the previous section, the narratives of both SSP3 and SSP4 imply a deterioration in most democratic characteristics: participation and representation are actively suppressed or eroded, inequalities are increasing (especially in SSP4), and accountability is dismantled, especially in the case of the authoritarian regimes assumed in SSP3. In contrast, projections for SSP3 and SSP4 in the case of the Gender Inequality Index, the Rule of Law Index, and the Control of Corruption index are expected to be stable between 2020 and 2050, showing even improvement for some countries. Similarly, even in the widespread regional conflicts expected in SSP3, the Human Development Index, Government Effectiveness, and the share of population in extreme poverty do not decrease for almost any country between 2020 and 2050.

Apart from SSP3 and SSP4 where differences between narratives and quantitative variables are more acute, divergences can be found in the other SSPs. While SSP2 aims to be the “middle-of-the-road” narrative that continues current trends, it tends to be more optimistic with values closer to SSPs 1 and 5, especially for the Human Development Index, Rule of Law, and Government Effectiveness. Similarly, SSP1 and SSP5 seem to be similar in terms of the evolution of the examined variables, implying a similar progress in improving all aspects of democratic government. Nevertheless, their narratives show important differences in the quality of democracy. For instance, the narrative of SSP5 shows a world that is much more technocratic than the one of SSP1, where efficiency and competitiveness are prioritised compared to justice aspects and that vulnerable groups and countries still exist (see Section 4.3.5 and Table 1 for more details). This would suggest a difference between the evolution of the Gender Inequality Index or the share of population in extreme poverty which is not found. An exception to these patterns is the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient that is used as a proxy to the justice characteristic, as its evolution from 2020 to 2050 matches with the expectation from the narratives. For instance, income inequality between countries is reduced in SSP1 and SSP5, it is more or less continuing in SSP2, and is exacerbated in SSP3 and, especially, SSP4.

Similar patterns are found by zooming in Europe (see Section 8.4 in the Appendix). For all SSPs, most proxy variables that were examined are improved for all countries between 2020 and 2050, usually reducing the gap between Eastern and Western European countries and between EU countries and Balkan countries, Turkey, Ukraine, and even Russia. Exceptions can be found for some variables, such as the Rule-of-Law Index in SSP2 and SSP3 where it is reduced in Ukraine and Russia and stays relatively stable in other countries (Figure 24). As in the global level, these results indicate that despite the stated differences between the SSP narratives, the examined quantitative proxy indicators assume a Europe that democratic values are improving in this century, in contrast to the reality of the democratic backsliding that we recently experience in many European countries.

Turning to the second part of the analysis, the main message is that, in most scenarios from the IPCC AR6 ensemble, global regions that score high in indicators related to democratic characteristics tend to perform well in climate change mitigation. Specifically, regions that have, on average, high Government Effectiveness, Rule-of-Law, and Control of Corruption in 2020, they tend to achieve significant reductions of CO₂ emissions and energy intensity between 2020 and 2050. These rather intuitive findings relate to the impact of institutional quality in addressing the climate crisis (including aspects of effectiveness and accountability), and

largely align with the available empirical evidence (Lindvall & Karlsson, 2024). It is, however, noted that these positive correlations are found among scenarios that follow SSPs 1, 2, and 5 and there is significant uncertainty in scenarios that follow SSPs 3 and 4. A potential explanation for this can be found in the uneven development or the conflicts among countries and regions that are assumed in SSP4 and SSP3 respectively, which may accentuate barriers to climate action even for countries that have high institutional capacity. In contrast, development is suggested to evolve in a relatively more uniform way in the other SSPs, especially in SSP1 and SSP5.

Other findings from the scenario ensemble can be less intuitive, such as the positive correlations found between the Human Development Index (a proxy for participation), the Gender Inequality Index (a proxy for representation), and the reductions in CO₂ emissions and energy intensity for SSP1, SSP2, and SSP5. For instance, in the context of sustainable development of SSP1 or following the current trends of SSP2, it can be expected that developed regions may reduce emissions faster and become more energy efficient (Soergel et al., 2021). However, the same is not expected for SSP5 where development is driven by fossil fuel. Another suggestion on this is that the increased economic growth of SSP1 and SSP5 may provide co-benefits both in terms of human development and gender inequality (which in turn can be related to increased democratic participation and representation) and in terms of emissions and energy efficiency. In contrast to all other proxy variables, the relationship between the examined mitigation indicators and the two distributive justice proxies (the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient and the share of population in extreme poverty) was much more uncertain in all SSPs. This may reflect the complex relationship between justice and climate action, at least in the way that this is represented in the models used to run the IPCC AR6 scenarios (Low et al., 2025). Nevertheless, it should be reiterated that these findings reflect assumptions about democratic governance embedded in the scenario results, and do not serve as evidence of an actual correlation between democracy and climate action in the real world.

6.3 Recommendations and next steps

The findings of this study highlight several opportunities to enhance the SSP framework so that it more accurately reflects democratic governance within scenarios and related modelling exercises. Given the central role of the SSP framework in the IPCC's Assessment Reports, improvements are essential to ensure that the assessed futures and scenarios account for political realities and complexities, while also examining more participatory, just, and inclusive climate transition pathways. The latter was one of the main findings from the narrative analysis, which found that, apart from SSP1, most SSP narratives present futures that are technocratic or elite-driven and do not emphasise participation, institutional responsiveness, and justice elements. While SSPs are mostly used by the modelling community, this extension could be supported by political scientists and by projects that explore the intersection of democratic governance and climate action such as RETOOL. In collaboration with climate-economy modellers, political scientists could provide the theoretical and empirical background to enrich the existing five narratives with more assumptions about democratic structures, institutions, and movements. Additionally, they could suggest additional narratives that go beyond the technocratic optimism of the existing ones, narratives driven by participation or justice aspects, or even narratives that explore alternative economic models (e.g., degrowth—see Savin & van den Bergh, 2024) along with their respective governance structures.

Apart from strengthening the SSP narratives, the political science and climate-economy modelling communities could also collaborate on improving the alignment of the quantitative elements of the SSPs with their narratives in the context of governance and democracy. As shown in the quantitative analysis, the evolution of most democracy-related variables shows little diversity over the first half of the century between SSPs, with the majority being overoptimistic (e.g., government efficiency never deteriorates even with the SSP3 conflicts). In addition, all variables change linearly over the years and oftentimes in tandem with each other. For instance, while all SSP quantifications assume that human development and government effectiveness improve together to different levels, there is no quantified narrative that explores a world with high government effectiveness and low human development. Building on empirical evidence from political science research, additional indicators could be incorporated, covering political elements beyond effective governance, such as democratic

participation, deliberation, and justice but also democratic legitimacy and institutional resilience. Both new and existing indicators could be adjusted to exhibit greater variation across SSPs, covering, thus, a larger part of the uncertainty space. Shocks and democratic backsliding such as the ones recently witnessed in the USA and Europe could be also explored in narratives and their quantitative representations. This could also help mainstreaming the study of discontinuities and extreme events in integrated assessment modelling (Gambhir et al., 2021; McCollum et al., 2020), thereby moving beyond the limitations of linear modelling approaches.

The cooperation between political scientists and modellers can also extend beyond the enrichment of the SSP frameworks and shape the scenario studies themselves. While this analysis suggested that relationships between various democracy-related assumptions and mitigation impacts in IPCC AR6 scenarios align with empirical evidence (e.g., that effective governments can enable climate action), these relationships are mostly implicit in the models. Most modelling studies used specific SSP narratives to inform basic drivers in the models such as GDP and population and not to explicitly study mitigation impacts of aspects such as governance in their scenarios. The above recommendations for enhancing SSP quantifications can support modellers in exploring a broader range of scenario variations by more fully integrating governance and political dimensions, thereby reducing the current overreliance on SSP2 within the scenario ensemble. Moreover, future modelling studies can explore the interactions between climate action and democratic governance in more detail, by assessing scenarios with different democratic institutions and structures, levels of participation, and expressions of justice in various countries. RETOOL can play potentially an important role in this direction, by providing a wealth of research on different domains of democracy in Europe which could potentially feed future modelling studies. RETOOL researchers already organised a first meeting with IAM modellers in June 2025 to assess future collaborations in these topics. A more extensive meeting is planned for autumn 2025 to advance synergies between RETOOL and other model-intensive projects, with the aim of addressing several of the recommendations outlined in this deliverable.

7 References

- Andrijevic, M., Cuaresma, J. C., Muttarak, R., & Schleussner, C. (2019). Governance in socioeconomic pathways and its role for future adaptive capacity. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0405-0>
- Andrijevic, M., Zimm, C., Moyer, J. D., Muttarak, R., & Pachauri, S. (2025). Representing gender inequality in scenarios improves understanding of climate challenges. *Nature Climate Change*, 15, 550–558. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-02242-5>
- Beck, S., & Oomen, J. (2021). Imagining the corridor of climate mitigation – What is at stake in IPCC’s politics of anticipation? *Environmental Science & Policy*, 123, 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.05.011>
- Bernauer, T., & Gampfer, R. (2013). Effects of civil society involvement on popular legitimacy of global environmental governance. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(2), 439–449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.01.001>
- Bretschger, L. (2024). Green Road is open: Economic pathway with a carbon price escalator. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 127, Article 103033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2024.103033>
- Brawley-Chesworth, A., Moore, B., Torney, D., & Oberthür, S. (2024). *D2.1– Analytical Framework*. RETOOL project. <https://www.retoolproject.eu/sites/default/files/2024-11/D2.1%20Analytical%20Framework.pdf>
- Buhaug, H., & Vestby, J. (2019). On growth projections in the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. *Global Environmental Politics*, 19(4), 118–132. https://doi.org/10.1162/glep_a_00525
- Burck, J., Uhlich, T., Bals, C., Höhne, N., & Nascremento, L. (2024). *Climate Change Performance Index 2025*. GermanWatch. <https://ccpi.org/wp-content/uploads/CCPI-2025-Results-1.pdf>
- Calliari, E. (2016). Loss and damage: A critical discourse analysis of Parties’ positions in climate change negotiations. *Journal of Risk Research*, 21(6), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2016.1240706>
- Calvin, K., Dasgupta, D., Krinner, G., Mukherji, A., Thorne, P. W., Trisos, C., Romero, J., Aldunce, P., Barrett, K., Blanco, G., Cheung, W. W., Connors, S., Denton, F., Diongue-Niang, A., Dodman, D., Garschagen, M., Geden, O., Hayward, B., Jones, C., . . . Ha, M. (2023). *IPCC, 2023: Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Core Writing Team, H. Lee and J. Romero (eds.)]*. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.59327/ipcc/ar6-9789291691647>
- Carrington, D. (2025, February 4). Climate change target of 2C is ‘dead’, says renowned climate scientist. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/feb/04/climate-change-target-of-2c-is-dead-says-renowned-climate-scientist>
- Clift, B., & Kuzemko, C. (2024). The social construction of sustainable futures: how models and scenarios limit climate mitigation possibilities. *New Political Economy*, 29(5), 755–769. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563467.2024.2342302>
- Clulow, Z. (2018). Democracy, electoral systems and emissions: explaining when and why democratization

- promotes mitigation. *Climate Policy*, 19(2), 244–257.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2018.1497938>
- Crespo Cuaresma, J. (2017). Income projections for climate change research: A framework based on human capital dynamics. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 226–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.02.012>
- Crespo Cuaresma, J., Fengler, W., Kharas, H., Bekhtiar, K., Brottrager, M., & Hofer, M. (2018). Will the Sustainable Development Goals be fulfilled? Assessing present and future global poverty. *Palgrave Communications*, 4(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-018-0083-y>
- Cuaresma, J. C., & Lutz, W. (2024). The demography of human development and climate change vulnerability: A projection exercise. *Vienna Yearbook of Population Research 2015, 2015*, 241–262.
- Dellink, R., Chateau, J., Lanzi, E., & Magné, B. (2017). Long-term economic growth projections in the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 200–214.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.06.004>
- Dryzek, J. S., Bowman, Q., Kuyper, J., Pickering, J., Sass, J., & Stevenson, H. (2019). *Deliberative global governance*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108762922>
- Dubash, N., Mitchell, C., Lerum, E., Borbor-Córdova, M., Fifita, S., Haites, E., Jaccard, M., Naidoo, S., Romero-Lankao, P., Aasen, M., Bashmakov, I., Bertoldi, P., Bhatia, P., Boykoff, M., Garg, A., Geden, O., Germeshausen, R., Niklas, G., Germany, H., . . . Lisboa, G. (2023). National and sub-national policies and institutions. In *Cambridge University Press eBooks* (pp. 1355–1450).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157926.015>
- Eisenack, K., Moser, S. C., Hoffmann, E., Klein, R. J. T., Oberlack, C., Pechan, A., Rotter, M., & Termeer, C. J. A. M. (2014). Explaining and overcoming barriers to climate change adaptation. *Nature Climate Change*, 4(10), 867–872. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2350>
- Euronews. (2021, June 29). Why democracy is the key ingredient to battling climate change. *Euronews*.
<https://www.euronews.com/green/2021/06/29/why-democracy-is-the-key-ingredient-to-battling-climate-change>
- Farrelly, M. (2019). *Discourse and democracy: Critical analysis of the language of government*. Routledge.
- Foster, G. (2020). Concrete utopianism in integrated assessment models: Discovering the philosophy of the shared socioeconomic pathways. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 68, 101533.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101533>
- Gambhir, A., George, M., McJeon, H., Arnell, N. W., Bernie, D., Mittal, S., Köberle, A. C., Lowe, J., Rogelj, J., & Monteith, S. (2021). Near-term transition and longer-term physical climate risks of greenhouse gas emissions pathways. *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01236-x>
- Gills, B., & Morgan, J. (2019). Global Climate Emergency: after COP24, climate science, urgency, and the threat to humanity. *Globalizations*, 17(6), 885–902.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2019.1669915>
- Godfrey, M. K. (2025, January 7). *Why climate action demands democracy* | *Journal of Democracy*. *Journal of Democracy*. <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/online-exclusive/why-climate-action-demands-democracy/>
- Harding, R., & Wantchekon, L. (2010). *The Political Economy of Human Development*. United Nations Development Programme. <https://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/hdrp201029.pdf>

- Hermwille, L., Schulze-Steinen, M., Brandemann, V., Roelfes, M., Vrontisi, Z., Kesküla, E., Anger-Kraavi, A., Trembaczowski, Ł., Mandrysz, W., Muster, R., & Zygmunt-Ziemianek, A. (2023). Of hopeful narratives and historical injustices – An analysis of just transition narratives in European coal regions. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 104, 103263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103263>
- Hossu, C., Oliveira, E., & Niță, A. (2022). Streamline democratic values in planning systems: A study of participatory practices in European strategic spatial planning. *Habitat International*, 129, 102675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2022.102675>
- Hulme, M. (2022). *Climate Change*. 1st Edition. Routledge.
- Jensen, A. V. (2025). Educating for Democracy? Going to College Increases Political Participation. *British Journal of Political Science*, 55, e1. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007123424000486>
- Jones, M. D., & McBeth, M. K. (2010). A narrative policy framework: Clear enough to be wrong? *Policy Studies Journal*, 38(2), 329–353. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2010.00364.x>
- Jones, M.D., McBeth, M.K., Shanahan, E.A. (2014). Introducing the Narrative Policy Framework. In: Jones, M.D., Shanahan, E.A., McBeth, M.K. (eds) *The Science of Stories*. Palgrave Macmillan, New York. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137485861_1
- Kanerva, J., & Krizsán, A. (2021). Discouraging climate action through implicit argumentation: An analysis of linguistic polyphony in the Summary for Policymakers by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. *Discourse & Communication*, 15(6), 609–628. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17504813211026512> (Original work published 2021)
- KC, S., Moradhvaj, Potancokova, M., Adhikari, S., Yildiz, D., Mamolo, M., Sobotka, T., Zeman, K., Abel, G., Lutz, W., & Goujon, A. (2024). Wittgenstein Center (WIC) Population and Human Capital Projections—2023 (Version V13) [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10618931>
- Krawczyk, F., & Braun, A. (2025). Models like heroes? Making Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) ready for deep decarbonization and a socio-economic transformation. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 121, 103959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.103959>
- Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., Hallegatte, S., Ebi, K. L., Kram, T., Riahi, K., Winkler, H., & van Vuuren, D. P. (2014). A new scenario framework for climate change research: The concept of shared climate policy assumptions. *Climatic Change*, 122(3), 401–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0971-5>
- Leininger, J., Buhaug, H., Gilmore, E., Lindberg, S. I., Andrijevic, M., Bauer, N., Jewell, J., Moyer, J., Soergel, B., Tosun, J., Vesco, P., Wingers, C., Hegre, H., Vestby, J., Kriegler, E., van Vuuren, D., Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, S. I., Brutschin, E., Nord, M., ... van Ruijven, B. (2024). Climate Futures are Political Futures: Integrating Political Development Into the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14387075>
- Leino, M., & Kulha, K. (2023). Hopes over fears: Can democratic deliberation increase positive emotions concerning the future? *Futures*, 154, 103246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2023.103246>
- Low, S., Brutschin, E., Baum, C. M., & Sovacool, B. K. (2025). Expert perspectives on incorporating justice considerations into integrated assessment modelling. *Npj Climate Action*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-025-00218-5>
- Mathias, J.-D., Debeljak, M., Deffuant, G., Diemer, A., Dierickx, F., Donges, J. F., Gladkykh, G., Heitzig, J., Holtz, G., Obergassel, W., Pellaud, F., Sánchez, A., Trajanov, A., Videira, N., Wilk, B., Wehkamp, J., Bhowmik, A. K., Cassar, A., Bruhn, T., & Milkoreit, M. (2020). Grounding social foundations for

- integrated assessment models of climate change. *Earth's Future*, 8(6), e2020EF001573. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EF001573>
- McCollum, D. L., Gambhir, A., Rogelj, J., & Wilson, C. (2020). Energy modellers should explore extremes more systematically in scenarios. *Nature Energy*, 5(2), 104–107. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0555-3>
- Mendelberg, T., Karpowitz, C. F., & Oliphant, J. B. (2014). Gender Inequality in Deliberation: Unpacking the Black Box of Interaction. *Perspectives on Politics*, 12(1), 18–44. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1537592713003691>
- Nomikos, W. G. (2025, April 8). *Understanding the Connection between Democracy and Climate Change*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/92k9q19c>
- O'Neill, B. C., Carter, T. R., Ebi, K., Harrison, P. A., Kemp-Benedict, E., Kok, K., Kriegler, E., Preston, B. L., Riahi, K., Sillmann, J., van Ruijven, B. J., van Vuuren, D., Carlisle, D., Conde, C., Fuglestvedt, J., Green, C., Hasegawa, T., Leininger, J., Monteith, S., & Pichs-Madruga, R. (2020). Achievements and needs for the climate change scenario framework. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(12), 1074–1084. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00952-0>
- O'Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Ebi, K. L., Kemp-Benedict, E., Riahi, K., Rothman, D. S., van Ruijven, B. J., van Vuuren, D. P., Birkmann, J., Kok, K., Levy, M., & Solecki, W. (2017). The roads ahead: Narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.01.004>
- Oberthür, S., Von Homeyer, I., Schewe, L., & Moore, B. (2025). Public participation in EU climate governance: the underexploited potential of national energy and climate plans. *Journal of European Integration*, 47(2), 257–276. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2025.2460194>
- Otto, D., Thoni, T. E., Wittstock, F., & Beck, S. (2021). Exploring narratives on negative emissions technologies in the post-Paris era. *Frontiers in Climate*, 3, 684135. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.684135>
- Paterson, M., Wilshire, S., & Tobin, P. (2023). The rise of Anti-Net zero populism in the UK: Comparing rhetorical strategies for climate policy dismantling. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis Research and Practice*, 26(3–4), 332–350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2023.2242799>
- Pedde, S., Kok, K., Hölscher, K., Oberlack, C., Harrison, P. A., & Leemans, R. (2019). Archotyping shared socioeconomic pathways across scales: an application to central Asia and European case studies. *Ecology and Society*, 24(4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/es-11241-240430>
- Peters, G. P., Al Khourdajie, A., Sognaes, I., & Sanderson, B. M. (2023). AR6 scenarios database: An assessment of current practices and future recommendations. *Npj Climate Action*, 2(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00050-9>
- Pickering, J., Bäckstrand, K., & Schlosberg, D. (2020). Between environmental and ecological democracy: theory and practice at the democracy-environment nexus. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 22(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908x.2020.1703276>
- Poznic, M., & Hillerbrand, R. (2021). Scenarios as tools of the scientific imagination: The case of climate projections. *Perspectives on Science*, 29(1), 36–61. https://doi.org/10.1162/posc_a_00360
- Rao, N. D., Sauer, P., Gidden, M., & Riahi, K. (2019). Income inequality projections for the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). *Futures*, 105, 27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2018.07.001>
- Riahi, K., van Vuuren, D. P., Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., O'Neill, B. C., Fujimori, S., Bauer, N., Calvin, K., Dellink,

- R., Fricko, O., Lutz, W., Popp, A., Crespo Cuaresma, J., KC, S., Leimbach, M., Jiang, L., Kram, T., Rao, S., Emmerling, J., Ebi, K., Hasegawa, T., Havlik, P., Humpenöder, F., Aleluia Da Silva, L., Smith, S., Stehfest, E., Bosetti, V., Eom, J., Gernaat, D., Masui, T., Rogelj, J., Strefler, J., Drouet, L., Krey, V., Luderer, G., Harmsen, M., Takahashi, K., Baumstark, L., Doelman, J. C., Kainuma, M., Klimont, Z., Marangoni, G., Lotze-Campen, H., Obersteiner, M., Tabeau, A., & Tavoni, M. (2017). The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009>
- Rohat, G. (2018). Projecting drivers of human vulnerability under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(3), 554. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15030554>
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (1999). *Corruption and Government: Causes, Consequences, and Reform*. Cambridge University Press; Cambridge Core. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139175098>
- Ross, A., Van Alstine, J., Cotton, M., & Middlemiss, L. (2021). Deliberative democracy and environmental justice: evaluating the role of citizens' juries in urban climate governance. *Local Environment*, 26(12), 1512–1531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1990235>
- Savin, I., & van den Bergh, J. (2024). Reviewing studies of degrowth: Are claims matched by data, methods and policy analysis? *Ecological Economics*, 226, 108324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108324>
- Schedler, A., Diamond, L., & Plattner, M. F. (Eds.). (1999). *The Self-Restraining State*. Lynne Rienner Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781685854133>
- Selseng, T., Linnerud, K., & Holden, E. (2021). Unpacking democracy: The effects of different democratic qualities on climate change performance over time. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 128, 326–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.12.009>
- Shanahan, Elizabeth A., Michael D. Jones, and Mark K. McBeth. "Policy narratives and policy processes." *Policy studies journal* 39.3 (2011): 535-561 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2011.00420.x>
- Soergel, B., Kriegler, E., Weindl, I., Rauner, S., Dirnaichner, A., Ruhe, C., Hofmann, M., Bauer, N., Bertram, C., Bodirsky, B. L., Leimbach, M., Leininger, J., Levesque, A., Luderer, G., Pehl, M., Wingens, C., Baumstark, L., Beier, F., Dietrich, J. P., ... Popp, A. (2021). A sustainable development pathway for climate action within the UN 2030 Agenda. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(8), 656–664. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01098-3>
- Sognaes, I., & Peters, G. (2025). Influence of individual models and studies on quantitative mitigation findings in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5698716/v1>
- UNDP (2024). *Democracy: A Cornerstone for Human Development*. UNDP. <https://www.undp.org/latin-america/blog/democracy-cornerstone-human-development>
- van Vuuren, D. P., Riahi, K., Calvin, K., Dellink, R., Emmerling, J., Fujimori, S., KC, S., Kriegler, E., & O'Neill, B. (2017). The Shared Socio-economic Pathways: Trajectories for human development and global environmental change. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 148–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.10.009>
- Wang, G., & Huan, C. (2023). Negotiating climate change in public discourse: insights from critical discourse studies. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 21(2), 133–145.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17405904.2023.2198725>

Weston, P. (2025, February 6). Jeff Bezos fund ends support for climate group amid fears billionaires 'bowing down' to Trump. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/feb/06/jeff-bezos-climate-group-trump-bezos-earth-fund-science-based-targets-initiative-decarbonisation-aoe>

8 Appendix

8.1 Use of SSPs in the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble

Figure 12. Use of SSPs across different policy categories in the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble

8.2 Percentage change of democratic characteristics proxies

Figure 13. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 14. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 15. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 16. Projections of the Government Effectiveness Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 17. Projections of the Gini Income Inequality Coefficient per country based on the SSP extensions

8.3 Additional proxies of democratic characteristics in the SSPs

Figure 18. Projections of Mean Years of Education per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 19. Projections of Control of Corruption Index per country based on the SSP extensions

Figure 20. Projections of population share in extreme poverty per country based on the SSP extensions

8.4 SSP proxies of democratic characteristics in Europe

Figure 21. Projections of the Human Development Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 22. Projections of the mean years of education in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 23. Projections of the Gender Inequality Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 24. Projections of the Rule-of-Law Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 25. Projections of Control of Corruption Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 26. Projections of Government Effectiveness Index in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 27. Projections of Gini Income Inequality Coefficient in Europe based on the SSP extensions

Figure 28. Projections of population share in extreme poverty in Europe based on the SSP extensions